

Report documenting the training of all field teams in the use of the protocols, SOPs and supporting tools

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Abbreviations

ARC	Agricultural Research Council, South Africa
BUNASOLS	Bureau National des Sols, Burkina Faso
CCO	Central Coordinating Office
CS	Country supervisor
EU	European Union
FARA	Forum for Agricultural Research in Africa, Ghana
LUCAS	Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey (EC)
FNSSA	Food, Nutrition, Security and Sustainable Agriculture
GPS	Geographic Positioning System
IBEC	Interbalkan Environment Centre
ICRAF	International Centre for Research in Agroforestry
IFA	Institut Facultaire des Sciences Agronomiques de Yangambi, DRC
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
IRA	Institut des Régions Arides, Tunisia
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
JRC	Joint Research Centre – European Commission
KALRO	Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization
MATE	Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (former SZIU, Szent István University)
ODK	Open Data Kit
PSU	Primary Sampling Unit
RHC	Regional Hub Coordinator
SDMT	Survey Data Management Tool
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SSU	Secondary Sampling Unit
TOT	Training of Trainers
TSU	Tertiary Sampling Unit
WU-DOW	Wageningen University, Department of Environmental Sciences
WUR	Wageningen University & Research
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

In the framework of the implementation of the European Union (EU) funded Soils4Africa project, training and capacity building of the partner organizations and others that would be involved in the field campaign is a major activity of Work Package 4 (WP4), which is about the field campaign. The management of the field campaign requires the development of protocols, electronic data recording forms, and standard operating procedures (SOP) for all activities relating to data collection from the field, sample processing, packaging and sample shipment and includes development of tools and templates for reporting. The management of the field campaign further includes developing an operational strategy and putting an organization in place that will allow for the effective and efficient implementation of the survey activities.

The training and capacity building exercise serves to train operational staff on the protocols and SOPs, and on the use of the tools, and to instruct surveyors as well as managers on how to best organize and plan for the field campaign. The training reflects the way the project has organized and structured the field campaign for the whole of Africa. The field campaign is conducted at country level and overseen by a Country Supervisor (CS), but it is coordinated at the regional level by the regional hub coordinator. Therefore, training is provided at the regional hub level, with participation of country supervisors from that region. The country supervisor subsequently trains the field surveyors in their country. The training at regional level was organized by the field campaign central coordinating office (CCO) and hosted by each of the regional hubs. This training at regional level is in effect a 'Training of Trainers' (ToT) on how the field survey is conducted and at the same time a training of the supervisors on how to manage and coordinate the field survey activities. This training is therefore comprehensive, and the members of the regional hub coordinator are trained to be able to provide support to their country supervisors as a follow-up, when and if needed, with the CCO stepping in only as a last resort.

This approach of stepping down the training to the various levels will only work if all the steps in the process of the management and the coordination, as well as of the survey itself, are standardized and fully documented. Also, instruction materials need to be available for training at the lower levels to be effective. The project made a great effort to have all these training materials available, including videos that can be used by the surveyor as a reference and self-teaching resource.

This deliverable reports on the training and capacity building efforts of the project up to the regional hub level and presents all the training materials that have been developed.

2. Setup and general outline of the training workshop

The typical outline of the training and planning workshop consist of the following elements (a typical training program is provided in Annex A):

1. Explanation of the protocol for the standard sampling sites and hands-on demonstration of the tools (including ODK form for data recording, tools for navigation in the field)
2. Instructions for the data management of the field campaign and use of the SDMT (including the app for generating QR codes)
3. Protocol for the survey of the reference site and use of the ODK form for data recording.
4. Planning and budgeting for the field campaign and use of the budgeting template.
5. Field day to demonstrate implementation of the protocols for both standard and reference sites and to practice use of the ODK forms for data recording and navigation in the field.

The purpose of the regional training workshop is to introduce and explain the protocol for the field survey, the protocol for the field campaign management, and the standard operating procedures. The objectives are to train country supervisors and regional hub coordinators on the use of tools so that they can in turn instruct their surveyors, and on how to undertake the planning and budgeting for the field campaign. As far as the planning and budgeting are concerned, the workshop serves as the first stage in the contract negotiations for conducting the field campaign. In this project contractual agreements are made with the executing institution for each country where the field campaign will be implemented. Doing the tentative planning and budgeting during the training workshop provided insight in the complexities and costing of the field campaign activities and helped enormously to shorten the process of reaching an agreement on the terms and conditions for implementing the field campaign, including finances. A template was developed for planning: which specifies the number of field teams required and the average time a team will spend in the field, for example, and for budgeting. For both activities it is important to make a good estimate of the time needed to do the survey, which will depend on the time needed to complete one Primary Sampling Unit (PSU), as well as the travel time needed to reach the various sampling points. To get such an estimate, trips are tentatively planned to connect the PSUs in a particular region, assuming the survey is conducted by somebody from that region. During the workshop, filling the template is done jointly by taking one country as example, while the country supervisors work at the same time on filling the template for their own country. We generally give the CSs two weeks to present the budget for the campaign in their respective countries. In practice, they take longer to complete this task.

For explaining the protocol for the field survey, we follow the protocol step by step, having first handed out the protocols in the language used by the participants. The explanation is done in either English or French asking to participants to comment and make corrections to the protocol in their own language (e.g., Arabic or Portuguese, but also French versions). At the same time, we showed instruction videos on the various aspects of the protocol (e.g., how to take a sample using the various tools, how to navigate in the field). The videos are effective in showing how the tasks are done, and the CS will also use these videos to instruct their field teams. The videos are intended for self-teaching and the CS should therefore know the content of the videos when they are referring to them. All video instruction materials are available on the project website, in the same language that are also used for the protocols.

After explaining the protocol, we take the participants through the Open Data Kit (ODK) form. We explain the forms while they are following on their phones, getting acquainted with the use of ODK at the same time. This is all done online. We assist participants in creating their accounts on the Ona.io platform and provide them with access to the Soils4Africa ODK forms so that they can get hands-on experience while the ODK form is explained. The form has a complex structure in that it branches in different directions depending on the answers that are given. It is therefore important to demonstrate each branch in the questionnaire, which is time-consuming. It is pertinent that each participant practices with the ODK form and we demand that each participant uses his/her own phone to record the data during the practice day in the field.

Regarding the field campaign and survey data management, we follow the same approach. We take participants step by step, chapter by chapter through the instruction manual for the field campaign management and subsequently we explain and demonstrate the Survey Data Management Tool (SDMT). Country Supervisors are first onboarded to the SDMT in the role of CS such that they can then sign in and view and practice with the data for their country while we explain the functioning of the SDMT. In this manner, the CS can practice the validation of the primary sampling units using data from their own country. We guide them through the generation of QR codes and at the same time the CS generates the QR codes for their own country. In a similar manner, we demonstrate how prospective surveyors should upload their application onto

the system and how these applications are vetted and approved. We demonstrate how jobs (several PSUs) are assigned to surveyors, how the dashboard is used to monitor progress, and how the quality control on the data that has been uploaded is done using the SDMT. Finally, we show how the SDMT is used for reporting.

The same procedure is followed for the reference site. Participants are taken through the protocol after which we take them through the ODK-form. Participants would have been onboarded to the Ona.io platform already and would have direct access to the form and able to follow the instructions using the form on their own phone or tablet.

The field day is intended to practice navigation in the field, demonstrate and practice implementing the protocol for the field survey, for both the standard monitoring sites and the reference sites. Because time is often short, it is advisable to practice navigation in the field, using Maps.me as well as using a GPS device. Many of the participants do not have practical experience of navigating in the field, and certainly not using Maps.me. It gives them an impression on how accurate and precise these devices are and helps them appreciate where things may go wrong. The exercise also makes the CSs appreciate the type of support the surveyors may require and makes them vigilant on where it may go wrong. The success of the survey will depend much on whether the surveyor is able to identify and reach the exact location of the planned sampling point. Experience so far indicates that errors are quite frequently made.

For the CCO, as developers of the protocols and tools and as managers and coordinators of the overall field campaign, the purpose of the workshop is also to assess the capacity and skills of the country supervisors, both to use the tools as well as to follow the protocol and SOP. This will help determine their need for further technical support within the country and to advice accordingly.

In the first instance, the training and planning workshops were used to test the protocols, the operating procedures, and tools. For the protocols and instruction manual for the field campaign management, the question was whether they were logical and in line with their own practice, easy to understand and achievable. For the tools, the question was whether they were easy to use (whether the use is intuitive) since most participants are not accustomed to using such tools and many, especially the older people, were often not particularly experienced in using digital applications. Consequently, we made several changes to the protocol, SOPs, and the tools by implication, and several subsequent versions have been developed. Changes have been implemented as a result of our experiences during the first four training workshops and especially as a result of the experiences gathered during the field day. In particular, the protocol for the reference site has undergone major changes, because of time constraints and considerations with respect to the reliability and relevance of the observations (how specific can you or want to be).

Lastly, based on the experience with the implementation and execution of the field campaign in the various countries, a few adjustments to the SDMT (in particular) might be needed. Once the field campaign has started, major changes to the protocol will no longer be possible, but changes, or maybe some additional functionality to the SDMT, will be possible. Therefore, we value conducting monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) missions to the various countries to learn what went well and what went wrong. The MEL missions could be considered part of the training and capacity building activity, but it is outside the scope of this report. We will further report on the individual missions.

We generally schedule a 4-day training and planning workshop, but this seems to be too short generally. However, having a 5-day training workshop is often perceived as too long by participants and will reduce the efficiency and effectiveness of the training. The 4-day duration is a compromise, but it means that the regional hub coordinators have to make an additional effort in

providing a refresher course and/or support of the training of the field surveyors, especially if much time has passed after the CS has received the training and the start of the field campaign.

3. Training workshops conducted and planned

Table 1 provides an overview of the training workshops that have been conducted and the two that are still planned.

For the West Africa Hub, we took a different approach than for the other regional hubs. Firstly, because we have French and English-speaking countries, we organized a training event for each of these groups. Secondly, because Nigeria is by far the biggest country in the West Africa region (with the most sampling points) and the CCO is also located in Nigeria, the CCO took on the role of regional hub coordinator for Nigeria. In addition, we wanted to use the Nigerian team to test the tools and instruments that we had developed and use the field campaign in Nigeria as a test case for the implementation of the field campaign. The first training we organized was with the Nigerian team therefore and had a special character in that all the people that had been involved in developing the protocols, tools and instruments (including the IT people), were part of the workshop.

For the Ghana workshop, we invited the CSs from the remaining English-speaking countries: Liberia, Sierra Leone, and the Gambia, apart from the participants from Ghana, who were quite a few. For the training workshop in Burkina Faso, we invited the CSs from all French speaking countries. This workshop also allowed us to test the French versions of the protocol, ODK-form, and instruction manual. The representative from Senegal was prevented from travelling and could therefore not attend. These training workshops were conducted within the COVID-19 period with a lot of restrictions for travel and with cost implications.

Table 1. Overview of the training workshops conducted and planned.

SN	Hub	Country where training was held	Training venue	Number of participants	Date of training
1	West Africa Hub	Nigeria	IITA, Ibadan	8	28–29 March 2022
2	West Africa Hub	Ghana	CSIR- SRI, Kumasi	14	4-7 April 2022
3	West Africa Hub	Burkina Faso	BUNASOLS, Ouagadougou	19	11-14 April 2022
4	South Africa Hub	South Africa	Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch	19	7-10 June 2022
5	North Africa Hub	Tunisia	Institut des Régions Arides (IRA), Medenine	21	4-8 September 2022
6	East Africa Hub	Kenya	KALRO, Naivasha	33	8–11 November 2022
7	Central Africa Hub	Cameroon	Yaoundé	10	1-5 May 2023 (planned)
8	Central Africa Hub	DRC	Kinshasa	12	5-9 June 2023 (planned)

The training workshop for all regional hubs were originally scheduled for the first half of 2022. However, because of doubts about the availability of funds for the field campaign, the training workshops were put on a hold until the annual meeting planned for September 2022, when the decision on how to proceed was expected to be taken.

The training workshop for the Southern Africa region was the first to be affected. We decided to still have the training workshop in June, because we had already done much of the preparation. There was also the fear that further delaying the workshop would cause a considerable delay of the field campaign in the region because the current season for doing the field survey would be missed. The workshop for the Northern Africa region was held just one week prior to the annual meeting to be held in Tunisia, which gave the opportunity to save some costs.

The training for the East Africa Hub was planned only after approval was obtained from the September 2022 annual meeting to continue with the training workshops, and after we agreed on a strategy on how to proceed with the field campaign in view of the financial shortcomings.

Preparations for the regional workshops should not be underestimated. It requires that the country supervisors for each of the countries in the region are identified and then the scheduled dates should still fit within their own schedule. The process for selection of the country supervisors involves first to identify a number of candidates for each country and then having interviews with each of them individually, to see whether they qualify, whether they are available and committed, to find out whether there are any institutional hindrances, etc. We have gone through this process for each of the workshops that were organized, realizing how critical the selection of the country supervisor is for the success of the field campaign. In some cases, adjustments had to be made following the performance of the participants during the training workshops.

For the Central Africa hub, we propose likewise to follow a different approach. The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) being such a vast country and with so many sampling points to be done is best to be considered a region of its own. The CS will be assisted by field supervisors who take on a coordinating role for a region within DRC. They will act de facto as a country supervisor. We have already identified the 'field supervisors' and the training workshop is planned for early June 2023.

For Cameroon, preparations have started as well and candidates for the role of country supervisor have been identified. In case of Cameroon, we will train the field surveyors at the same time such that the field campaign can start immediately after the training workshop. The training workshop was planned for the first week of May 2023.

4. Summary Description of the Training Materials and Tools

The training workshops focused on five major aspects to build the capacity of the partners and all stakeholders involved in the field campaign. The aspects are:

- The protocol for the field survey
- The ODK form and standard operating procedures (SOP) for the standard monitoring sites
- Protocol for the field campaign management
- Survey data management tool (SDMT)
- The ODK forms and SOP for the reference sites including those for pesticide residues.

5.1 Protocol for the field survey

The protocol for the field survey is a set of guidelines for field surveyors on soil sample collection and field assessment of agricultural lands in Africa, for the purpose of soil quality monitoring. It is a standard protocol that applies to all the surveys that are conducted for this project across Africa, ensuring that results from different regions are comparable. It is intended for use by the field survey teams or surveyors as training material and as a reference document in the field, during the field survey. The field surveyor is, therefore, expected to fully understand the instructions given. At the same time, the protocol is intended for the country supervisors and hub coordinators who must manage the campaign within their country and who have to support the field surveyors in conducting their tasks. The regional hub coordinator needs to have an even more profound understanding of the protocol and methods presented, carrying the ultimate responsibility for the campaign within their African sub-region. We have developed the third version of the protocol, and expect no further major updates.

The protocol for the field survey is structured and essentially contains the following:

1. **Preparations and materials for fieldwork** – this session provides guidelines on what is required for the fieldwork, particularly on what to do before going to the field. It contains information on the materials required and their specifications, where and how to download the necessary apps and electronic forms needed for the survey, including the loading of coordinates into Maps.me or handheld GPS devices.
2. **Safety and Security issues** – This covers all the safety and security issues the surveyors need to be aware of, including relevant contacts in case of emergencies. It emphasizes the importance of getting permission from the landowner and community prior to sampling, as well as the need to carry with them all relevant documents authorizing their mission.
3. **Navigating in the field** – this is an important aspect of the field survey because proper field navigation has a direct impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of the work. The number of sampling points that could be done per day is directly related to mastery of field navigation. This section, therefore, contains information on how to navigate using a handheld GPS device, Maps.me, and the google maps app. The advantages and disadvantages of each of these items are stated in the document and demonstrated during the training.
4. **Rejection of a secondary or tertiary sampling unit** - The sampling design is a hierarchical design consisting of three stages. The primary sampling units (PSU) represent two-by-two (2x2) km spatial units from which several secondary sampling units (SSU), of one (1) ha in size, are randomly selected, and for each SSU there are several tertiary sampling units (TSUs) identified of 25m² each. For each SSU, one (1) TSU needs to be sampled. However, for reasons such as accessibility, security, poor terrains, etc., certain points may not qualify or might not be suited to take samples. For that purpose, alternative sampling points (TSUs) are identified for each SSU. For each PSU four (4) SSUs are

supposed to be sampled, but because an individual SSU may not qualify as a valid sampling unit, alternative SSUs are likewise identified and serve as backup sampling locations. This section specifies when and how to reject sampling points including the probable reasons.

5. **Layout and sampling procedure** – This section specifies the general layout of the sampling plot.
6. **Soil sample collection** – This entails information on how the soil samples should be collected at each sampling point and how to use the different tools for soil sample collection. It also indicates the number of samples to be collected.
7. **Labeling** - Bagging and labeling is an important aspect of quality assurance and needs to be properly done to make sure that the soil samples are correctly identified, also in the further process of handling and analysis. This section provides details regarding the bagging and labeling convention of soil samples.
8. **Land and Soil surface characterization** - Field observation data are to be collected from the sampling locations. Observations are made on soil properties (e.g., soil depth, stoniness, soil drainage), soil surface characteristics (soil erosion by water and wind, stoniness), and on the land and terrain (landform, slope). This section provides practical guides with many illustrative images of how these assessments need to be done properly.
9. **Observations on land use and land cover** - In this section the instructions are provided for the observations on land use and land cover. Because observations are made in the context of agricultural land and for the purpose of soil quality assessment, the land cover observations mainly serve to determine soil cover. Furthermore, observations are made on land and crop management, providing information on land use intensity which is important for the interpretation and evaluation of changes in soil condition and soil quality. Observations on land management include soil conservation measures and practices. Observations are also made regarding water management in terms of measures to increase the water supply to the crop (e.g., irrigation).
10. **What to do in special situations** – the protocol provides guidelines on what to do in some special situations, such as sampling a cultivated farm with prominent ridges or sampling at the border between fields or at the transition of one land use type to the other.

The protocol for the field survey is available in English, French, and Arabic, and they are accessible via <https://www.soils4africa-h2020.eu/field-campaign>. Major important parts of the protocol are also presented in the audio-visual form in video format and available online via https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB4Kq_AOaGwGLT9iY77wgm_CMNTA3xtvA (English), https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB4Kq_AOaGwHGHRsqTM-sPKboSpk6wLjK (French), https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB4Kq_AOaGwF5Qcf4D8zZx3zA3pePramw (Arabic). A-5 sized copies of the protocol for the field survey were presented and distributed to all country supervisors during the training, and copies were subsequently made by the country supervisors for their field surveyors.

5.2 The ODK form and standard operating procedures (SOP) for the standard monitoring sites

The electronic form, ODK form, developed for the soils4Africa project is implemented in the ODK-Collect App available on Android phones. It has a direct link with the Ona server where the data is stored after it has been uploaded. The surveyors are expected to have a functioning android phone on which the ODK-Collect app is downloaded through internet connection. Using the login credentials provided in the standard operating procedures (SOP), the surveyors are able to access and complete the form without having to connect to the internet during fieldtrip. Internet access is only required when uploading the form to the Ona.io server. The form is structured according to the protocol for the field survey. It contains important information ranging from the general description of the site to the details of the soil samples collected. The ODK collects important

information such as the date of the survey, surveyors name, GPS coordinates of the sampling point, sample ID, land and soil description, land cover and land use, and land and water management practices. It also gives the option to the surveyor to reject the sampling point if it is considered invalid with a set of procedures to follow. The ODK form is available in English, French, and Arabic. A Portuguese version is being developed. The language is selected when opening the ODK form.

The SOP is a step-by-step guide to the field survey and to how to use and complete the ODK form. It follows the protocol and may refer to the document for technical details. It clearly specifies what the surveyor needs to do before leaving for the field, what to do in the field, and what to do after returning from the field. It is a practical do-it-yourself handbook for the field survey. It is available in English, French, and Arabic online via: <https://www.soils4africa-h2020.eu/field-campaign>. A5-sized copies of the SOP were printed for all the country supervisors and distributed during the training workshops. We have had several updates and are currently using the third version.

5.3 Protocol for field campaign management

The protocol for the field campaign management serves as an instruction manual for the country supervisor and regional hub coordinator and provides a guide to the activities of the country supervisor especially with respect to the management and coordination of the field campaign. This document sets out the process of selection of candidates for the field surveyor position (and this may include the country supervisor his or her self) and granting of survey contracts; it specifies the support the CS is expected to give to the field surveyor, and how that support is arranged and organized, the responsibilities and tasks of the field supervisor vis-a-vis the CS, and further duties of the country supervisor. These duties include the recruitment of field surveyors, quality control of data from field observations, monitoring and reporting on the progress of the field survey, sample preparation, selection, shipment, and storage. The instruction manual highlights the technical support to be provided by the country supervisor to the surveyors and provides detailed information on how to provide such assistance. For instance, the generation of QR code labels for the soil samples; supplying materials such as GPS devices, providing means of transportation as well as establishing an effective channel of communication between the country supervisor and the different survey teams. Provided in the protocol for the field campaign management among others are:

- A standard text for the announcement of the call for the expression of interest for carrying out the field surveys for the Soils4africa project.
- Example of calculation of the number of survey teams.
- Budget allocation for individual teams and field survey assignment.
- Template for letter of agreement to conduct a field survey.
- Instructions for generating QR codes to serve as soil sample labels.

The protocol is available in English, French, and Arabic online via: <https://www.soils4africa-h2020.eu/field-campaign>. A5-sized copies of the instruction manual were printed and distributed to all country supervisors during the training workshops. The protocol has been updated to the second version.

5.4 Survey Data Management Tool (SDMT)

The SDMT is a web-based application designed specifically for the (data) management of the field campaign of Soils4Africa project across all countries. It provides a platform for data management that can be used by different level of users, each with their own role and authority. It has four (4) levels of users: the field surveyor who conducts the survey in the field and has no direct access but to upload the data; the country supervisor - who enlists and supervises the field surveyor, does the data quality control and monitors progress at country level; the regional hub coordinator who

supervises and monitors the activity of the country supervisor, does the 2nd level QC and monitors progress at regional level; and the Central Coordinating Officer -who does the onboarding of CSs and RHCs and any other user to the system, monitors progress at country and regional hub level and manages the entire campaign for continental Africa.

The SDMT has four (4) modules as follows:

- **Surveyors' application and the onboarding process:** This is the module that deals with the field surveyors' application and their inclusion (onboarding) in the field campaign. All field supervisors that participate in the field campaign passed through this module. Prospective surveyors send in their applications via: <https://sdmt.soils4africa-h2020.eu/surveyor/onboarding/>. Immediately after the application is submitted, the prospective surveyor receives an email message confirming their application and the status of the application. All submitted applications are available on <http://sdmt.soils4africa-h2020.eu/> and the CS can then log into the SDMT to reject or approve the applications. Once an application is approved or rejected, the surveyor immediately receives an email message indicating the status of their application, what they need to do next and how to do it.
- **Sampling points validation:** This module covers checking each of the predefined PSU and to ascertain that it is a valid sampling unit: accessible, valid agricultural land, and with no security threats. Under this module the country supervisor can accept or reject a PSU. Once a PSU is selected, the associated SSUs and TSUs are displayed, and one can zoom in further to see the underlying patterns of the satellite imagery as to whether it qualifies for acceptance or rejection. In the case of rejection, the country supervisor is required to provide reasons for the action. In providing these reasons, s/he is allowed to select option(s) from a predefined list and s/he is able to include additional specific reasons for rejecting the PSU. The country supervisor can also see the number of accepted, rejected (including the reasons), and unvalidated PSUs in the point validation module. A PSU can be allocated or assigned to a surveyor only after it has been validated and accepted (status is "accepted")
- **Job assignment and management:** This is the portal that allows the country supervisor to assign some sampling points (PSUs) to the surveyor whose application has been approved and to monitor and manage the activities of the surveyor. In the 'Jobs' portal, the country supervisor can see the total number of jobs assigned, jobs not started, jobs in progress, and jobs completed. S/He is also able to see the number of PSUs assigned by sampling job, the surveyors name, the number of submissions per surveyor, the status of each submission, and the end date of assigned jobs per surveyor.
- **Monitoring and quality control:** This is a module that allows the country supervisor to monitor the data submitted by the surveyors into the SDMT and to be able to perform quality control of those data. The quality control entails critically examining the submitted data, making minor corrections where needed and approving the submission or rejecting the submitted data in cases of significant errors that cannot be corrected by the country supervisor. The quality control procedure is likewise governed by rules and the different types of errors are categorized and coded while the CS can still provide additional detail on the error observed. The QC data is stored and can be viewed by the RHC for the 2nd level QC.

For further information and user instructions on the SDMT, see the full SDMT manual (<https://doi.org/10.25502/qba0-ww37/p>). The video documentation on how to use the SDMT and how to navigate through its different modules is available at: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLB4Kg_AOaGwHrbAW61xgXlmg_OulZshyN

5.5 The ODK forms and SOP for the reference sites including those for pesticide residues.

The Reference Sites in the Soils4Africa project are special sites where additional samples are collected and extra soil information is recorded. The 250 Reference Sites are not additional sites; they are selected from the 20.000 standard monitoring sites. Based on the complexity of the activity to be performed, two types of Reference Sites are distinguished.

On the **Minimalistic Reference (MRS) sites** unit-volume (surface, topsoil, and subsoil) samples, and a surface sample for pesticide residue analysis are collected, respectively. Contrary to the way samples from the standard monitoring sites are collected, these samples are taken from a “mini pit” of at least 50 cm deep (“mini-profile” description). The electronic ODK form developed for the MRS sites guides the surveyor through the process of recording information on site, sampling circumstances and scanning of barcodes. Additionally, a set of 12 question groups is integrated in the ODK form to record as much pedological information as possible considering the observable properties of the “mini-profile”. The questions are based on the World Reference Base for Soil Resources (WRB) criteria related to diagnostic units (horizons, properties, and materials), but are simplified in order to answer them without the need of any tool and laboratory data. These tasks should be performed at each of the 250 selected Reference Sites.

On the **Advanced Reference (ARS) sites** (on top of MRS site activities) full soil profile description, classification and sampling by genetic horizons are performed. The ODK form developed for the ARS Sites guides the surveyor through site, environment, soil, and soil horizon characterization based on the FAO Guidelines for Soil Description. Hosting ARS Sites and thus the performance of these advanced observations is a voluntary activity.

During the regional training workshops, the concept, SOPs and ODK forms for both types of reference sites are introduced during indoor and outdoor sessions (with demonstration). At each training workshop, the countries that show interest to host Reference Sites are defined. Since the total number of RS sites is only 250 across the entire continent, we focus on countries which have the capacity to perform the activities and where the PSUs represent high variability in agroecological zonation, soil and land use types, while making sure we also include possible hot spot areas in pesticide use. After the specification of the list of countries of interest we establish a cooperation between the CS and the members of the Reference Site “task force team” who support the CS in the selection of sites and provide technical assistance even on the field.

For the reference site, the protocol and standard operating procedure are combined. Please Annex B

6. Summary of Outcomes of the Training Workshops

This section presents the summary outcomes and conclusions of each of the training workshops as follows:

6.1 Summary outcomes and conclusions of the training workshops in West Africa Hub

The training workshops held in West Africa were used as pilot to gain a proper understanding and learn from the organization and the effectiveness of the capacity building workshops. Three workshops were held in West Africa, one in Nigeria, the others in Ghana and Burkina Faso. The workshops were done this way because of the peculiarities of West Africa. The workshop in Nigeria was organized because of the direct presence of IITA in Nigeria and as a test case of the tools for the training workshops to be subsequently conducted in other African countries. The workshop in Ghana and Burkina Faso were separated because of language barrier., The Ghana workshop was therefore for Anglophone while the Burkina workshop was for Francophone West Africa.

The participants were quite happy with the protocols and instruction manual. They expressed to have gained deep understanding of what the surveyors and country supervisors need to do. The CSs were taught how to generate the QR codes for sample labeling for their countries and did so during the training workshop.

They were guided to develop a budget for the field campaign in their respective countries and from the exercises in making a budget it was indicated that the funds required for the field campaign would largely exceed the funds that are available for the field campaign. It set the stage for negotiations and in case of Nigeria we were able to agree on a budget that, however, was still 25-30% over the funds that we would have available for the field campaign as calculated based on the budget allocated for this activity in the project. Final agreement on the budget is only made after the training workshop. In the Ghana workshop we did some pilot exercise in the planning of field trips to estimate the distances that need to be travelled and time required to conduct the survey, as input to the budgeting exercise.

The number of reference sites for each country was identified and the time windows for the field survey in the respective countries were specified. Comments were received on the then version of the protocols and tools presented, and these inputs were used to develop a revised version of all the training materials and tools for the subsequent workshops. Reports of the training in Nigeria, Ghana and Burkina Faso are provided in Annex Annex C, Annex D and Annex E respectively.

6.2 Summary outcomes and conclusions of the South Africa Hub training workshop

The training workshop held in the South Africa Hub has the following outcomes and conclusions:

- CS from all countries in the Southern Africa region participated in the workshop, apart from Angola for which we had not been able to identify a suitable candidate. The hub coordinators (or their representatives) from the North Africa Region, the East Africa, and Central Africa region were invited and attended the workshop. This was done to get the RHCs more involved in the project and also to prepare them a bit better for their role in the field campaign.

- All participants received the updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0) and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 2.0).
- The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that were presented. That is the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that seems to be well designed, and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable. As in the earlier workshops, some people had some difficulty picking it up; the younger people in general seemed to have fewer problems. It will require a lot of exercises before the tools can be used effectively and it requires the CS to arrange for technical support in using these tools locally or to be provided by the regional hub coordinator.
- Comments were received from all participants and these comments were implemented in the final version of all the training materials and tools. Especially the protocol for the minimalistic reference site would undergo major changes as result of the comments received during the field day.
- The same applies to the template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign. The template provides a good insight into the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters is the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day, depending on the efficiency of the surveyor but also on the distances and condition of the roads that need to be travelled). The template provides a way of calculating the sampling efficiency, but it is only by experience in the field that a correct estimate can be made. Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets to be discussed two weeks after the closing of the workshop.

The full training report of the South Africa Hub is provided in Annex F

6.3 Summary outcomes and conclusions of the North Africa Hub training workshop

The training workshop held in the South Africa Hub had the following outcomes and conclusions:

- Participants were from all countries in the North Africa Region and there were generally 2 or 3 representatives, sometimes even more from each country, to make the training more efficient (less need for a second within country training)
- All participants received the updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0), and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 3.0). The documents were made available in French, English, and Arabic and each participant was able to choose their preferred language.
- The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that we presented. That is, the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that seems to be well designed, and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable. As in the earlier workshops, some people had some difficulty picking it up; the younger people in general seemed to have fewer problems. It will require a lot of exercises before the tools can be used effectively and it requires the CS to arrange for technical support in using these tools locally or to be provided by the regional hub coordinator. The same applies to the template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign. The template provides a good insight into the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters remains the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day).
- Similar to what was done in South Africa, we elaborated the budget for the field campaign in Tunisia in plenary, to illustrate how the template works, while the country supervisors worked on their own budget. The budget for IRA and the results for the other countries at

the end of the exercise were far beyond the available funds. Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets, and think of way of reducing costs, to be discussed two weeks after the closing of the workshop.

- Using the 'consent form' for getting consent from farmers or farm managers in the field is not going to work in most cases of Africa as seen in north Africa in addition to previous similar experiences in West and South Africa. (The "consent form" was developed after the workshops held in West Africa, because of the concerns perceived on the alleged risk of EU not allowing publication of the point data without such consent.) Farmers are generally afraid to sign such documents as they easily misinterpret such consent to be giving away the ownership of their farms. Consent could generally be given but not formally and in cases where consent is not given the surveyors should go for the alternative backup points.
- The tentative budget has been done for all the countries of the northern Africa region. All of them showed budgets that exceed the available funds, to varying degrees, however. All countries would review their budgets and report back and we planned an online meeting within two weeks' time to discuss and finalize. It should be noted that the time for the validation of the PSUs is not included explicitly in budget calculations but is taken to be an integral part of the work of the country supervisor.
- Field survey was conducted in one of the actual sampling points close to Medenine. The point illustrated how complex the soil could be. It was a very useful exercise, because of the nature and conditions of the soils, with their calcic and petrocalcic horizons that are not found in other regions of Africa and that require adaptation of the method for taking soil samples, and which could be demonstrated. The data was recorded and uploaded to the SDMT where quality control was later done. The quality control procedures were explained and demonstrated to all participants using the sampled point.
- The weather condition is harsh and directly impact the number of time people could spend on the field. This shows that the amount of work people can do in a day is already limited by the weather condition. Generally, the fieldwork is possible between 6.00 to 10.00, and anytime beyond this becomes unbearable in the field. This needs to be factored into the budget. Field work can only be done during in the winter season

The full report of the north Africa Hub training workshop is in Annex G

6.4 Summary outcomes and conclusions of the East Africa Hub training workshop

The training workshop held in the East Africa Hub has the following outcomes and conclusions:

1. Participants from all countries of the East Africa Hub attended the workshop, apart from Eritrea, of which the representative was prevented from coming at the last moment and Madagascar that we had given a separate status (to be dealt with at a later stage). The representative of Sudan participated in the training workshop because Sudan was originally allocated to the EAH. However, for practical reasons Sudan was later allocated to the NAH.
2. The updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0), and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 3.0) were distributed to all participants. The documents were made available in French, English, and Arabic and each participant was able to choose their preferred language.
3. The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that we presented. That is the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that was well designed, and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable.
4. As in the earlier workshops, quite some people had difficulty picking up how the tools work and in using them. The younger people in general seemed to have fewer problems. This is related

to everything being formalized and standardized (protocols and procedures) and everything is done digitally. It will require a lot of exercises before the tools can be used effectively. It requires the CS to arrange for technical support in using these tools, to be provided locally or by the regional hub coordinator. Some had difficulty, while filling the form for the field survey, to download or get the coordinates because of their rather old phones that did not meet the specifications. It illustrates the importance that surveyors need to have the proper equipment, but also that these are tested well before going to the field. Some have already claimed new computers and phones. There is budget for phones and other needed equipment and that should be used.

5. The template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign is also considered complicated, but provides a good insight into the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters is the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day). The template provides a way of calculating the sampling efficiency, but it is only by experience in the field that a correct estimate can be made.

Like what was done in previous workshops, we elaborated the budget for the field campaign in Kenya in plenary, to illustrate how the template works, while the country supervisors worked on their own budget. The budget estimates for KALRO Kenya and the other countries at the end of the exercise were far beyond the available funds (twice the available budget). And that was also the case for the draft budgets for the other countries. One of the issues in Kenya budget was that they want to use their own staff for the field survey and want to apply the official per diem rates which would make the cost for the operation of the field teams per day too high, with even not having made any provision for covering for salary cost. It shows how complicated this issue is and that the CS needs to look for alternative ways to reduce costs (e.g., by making use of local extension agents). Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets to be discussed two weeks after the closing of the workshop. The discrepancy between the projected budget and the available funds is very large and it will not be possible to reconcile it apart from maybe in special cases (smaller countries).

6. No further changes are recommended with respect to the survey protocols, instruction manual for country supervisors, instruction videos, SOP and ODK form.

7. Using the 'consent form' for getting consent from farmers or farm managers in the field is not going to work for Kenya, like for other countries as we experienced in West, South, and North Africa. In this case it took us over an hour to get consent from the farmer because the farmer himself was not present on the farm and because there had been issues over land recently, people are very suspicious (even our presence in the area created suspicion). One farmer got very angry at his wife for allowing us even on the farm. (Farmers are generally afraid to sign such documents as they easily misinterpret such consent to be giving away the ownership of their farms.) So, the advice is that consent should generally be given but not formally. In cases where it takes a considerable amount of time to get consent, the surveyors should go for the backup point (don't wait too long; we generally calculate two hours for doing one PSU; that is four sampling points).

8. The tentative budget has been done for all the countries of the east Africa region. All of them showed budgets that exceed the available funds, generally by a factor of two. All countries would review their budgets and report back. It should be noted that the time for the validation of the PSUs is not included explicitly in budget calculations but is taken to be an integral part of the work of the country supervisor.

9. Field survey was conducted in one of the actual sampling points close to Naivasha. The point illustrated how dry and compact the soil can be with extreme difficulty in augering. The data

was recorded and uploaded to the SDMT where quality control was later done. The quality control procedures were explained and demonstrated to all participants using the sampled point.

10. We conducted a navigation exercise both at the place where the workshop was held and, in the field, navigating to the points to be sampled. In both cases people were not able to converge to the same point within 20 m accuracy. As a consequence, we are going to accept points sampled in the field if they are within 20m of the planned sampling point location.

The full report of the eastern Africa Hub training workshop is provided in Annex H

6.5 Summary outcomes and conclusions of the Central Africa Hub training workshop

For the Central Africa Hub we have planned two workshops, one for the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and one for Cameroon. We consider having one training workshop for CAH not effective. DRC is such a big country that it counts for a region in itself. We will divide DRC up into various regions with a Field Supervisor having the responsibility for the implementation of the field campaign in that region. He/she will have the same role as the country supervisor. Field supervisors have already been identified and the program of the workshop will not be different from the other workshops we have already conducted.

For Cameroon, being the second largest country in the region, we will organize a separate training, in which now also the field surveyors will participate. This eliminates the need for a second training for the field surveyors only and will make the training workshop more efficient and effective. Country supervisor and field surveyor have already been identified. We will run the same training program and we did not consider it very useful to further delay the issuing of the deliverable 4.3 until after these workshops have been conducted. As for all previous workshops we will issue a report on each training workshop individually.

7. Pictures from the Training Workshops

These are some of the pictures taken during the training and capacity building of the S4A field campaign across Africa.

Demonstrating the use of QR codes for sample labelling on the standard monitoring site in in Ghana

Demonstrating the protocols for the Advance Reference site in in Ghana

Participants of the training workshop for Anglophone CS WAH in Ghana

The workshop participants at one of the PSU in Burkina Faso

Participants of the training workshop for Francophone CS WAH in Burkina Faso

Visit to the soils laboratory of BUNASOL

Participants of the SAH training workshop at Stellenbosch University, Cape Town, South Africa

Demonstrating the Reference site protocol in South Africa

SAH CS at the standard monitoring sites in South Africa

Field visit by the NAH CSs to one of the TSU in Medenine

Participants of the NAH training workshop at IRA, Medenine, Tunisia

Dr Adam Csorba demonstrated the reference site sampling protocols at medenine

Soil sampling at Naivasha during the field visit

Participants of the EAH training workshop at Naivasha, Kenya

Dr Jeroen Huisling demonstrated the protocols for the standard monitoring site at one of the PSU in Naivasha

8. Conclusion

The approach the Project adopted for the implementation of the field campaign, to devolve responsibility for the execution of the field campaign to country supervisors and who, in turn, will engage surveyors and establish field teams to conduct the field campaign in the various regions of their country, places a very high demand on the training and capacity building activities in this project. It requires that all steps in the process, as well as all the protocols that are used, are fully documented, describing the smallest detail. This not only refers to the field survey itself, but also to the management of the campaign, including data management. It requires that the various processes are designed with a high level of detail, implemented in tools and apps that are then made available online. When all these processes are formalized and the implementation governed by these tools, there is little room for interpretation by the surveyor or field campaign manager and assures consistency and high quality of the work done and the data provided. We must consider that the surveyor can be more or less experienced and that the field campaign manager is more or less skilled in managing such campaigns and they need to be properly guided and facilitated in carrying out their tasks. It also implies that the protocols and the tools should not be too complex to use. To give an example, even the quality control is a fully formalized process in the SDMT tool, in which you select from several options to indicate the type of error that has occurred. We think we have been very successful in developing these tools and instruments.

The fact that we have thought through and documented the process, again in relation to the survey as well as data management related to the campaign, and developed the tools for data collection and data management has been new to all participants of the various workshops. That even applies for using online tools for data recording like the ODK form (not only for recording data in the field, but also for recording data in the lab for example). It has been highly appreciated and participants felt that they will benefit tremendously for their own work, beside that it facilitates the work they do for the project. This relates especially to the field campaign at country level and therefore to the CS, but also applies coordination at both the African sub-regional level, and for the RHC who is also facilitated. The training and capacity building activities is in the interest of the project but also serves a general interest in building the capacity of the people themselves.

This approach has some challenges. Many people lack the skills to effectively use all these digital tools and online apps, especially if they are somewhat older. They have difficulty creating accounts, going through the authentication process, or have difficulty understanding where things go wrong, and correct them if they do. We also observed that the 4-days training workshop is often not enough for participants to internalize all the actions they are required to take. Therefore, we have all the instruction materials online, but we also provided printed materials of the protocols and instruction manuals at all training workshops and, because not all people read very carefully, we provided instruction videos, not only on the various aspect of the field survey and sample collection, but also on the use of the SDMT. However, it still means that continued support is needed. We cannot assume that the country supervisor is able to give proper instruction to the surveyor on the use of procedures and tools. Also, it requires the CS to immediately supervise and directly monitor the work of the field surveyor, to be able to assist if anything goes wrong during the field work on with the upload of the data for example. The SDMT allows the CS to do that, and CS is also instructed to create a WhatsApp group with his/her surveyors to facilitate communication between them, which also enables the surveyors to assist each other.

In general, there is an important role to play for the regional hub coordinator in providing this continued support. Important in this respect is the monitoring, evaluation, and learning (MEL) from what is happening at country level and providing feedback to the central coordinating office as well

as to the country supervisor and his/her team. We organize meetings for the purpose of MEL and this needs to be institutionalized in the program of the RHC. This is also considered part of the capacity building but will not be discussed further in this report. In general, we may have underestimated the efforts required for training and capacity building for the field campaign to be successful.

Overall, we must conclude that a tremendous effort has been made, not only in the development of the tools and instruction materials, but also in the organization of the training workshops (though it took more time than planned) within a short time frame and under difficult conditions sometimes, and the project will continue to make that effort. It has so far been a success and highly appreciated by those who received the training.

ANNEX A: Typical training workshop program

Example of the training workshop program for regional hub coordinators and country supervisors:

DAY 1: Welcome, Introduction, protocols and tools

TIME	ACTIVITY
9:00 AM	Registration :
9:30 – 9:50 am	Welcome and Introduction of country supervisors, RHC and facilitators
9:50 – 10:30am	General introduction of the field campaign, and implementation plan - Purpose, objectives and the expected outcome of the training programme
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break
11:30 – 12:30 am	Introduction to the Protocol for the field survey - requirements and navigation
11:15 – 12:45	Protocol for the field survey -keynotes and technicalities
12:45 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH
1:45 – 2:30 pm	Protocol for field campaign management - Barcodes generation
2:30 – 4:30	Electronic data collection using ODK and the SOP -Demonstration and practice
4:30 – 4:35 pm	Feedbacks and Remarks

DAY 2: Survey data management tool (SDMT)

TIME	ACTIVITY
9:00 AM	Registration:
9:30 – 9:50 am	Overview of the SDMT and its functionalities - Surveyor’s application webpage
9:50 – 10:30am	SDMT Presentation and demonstration - Sampling point validation - Surveyors application and onboarding of surveyors
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break
11:30 – 12:45 am	SDMT Presentation and demonstration - Job assignment - Quality control - Onboarding of country supervisors
12:45 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH
1:45 – 3:30 pm	- Hands-on SDMT - Sampling point validation

3:30 – 4:00 pm	Feedbacks and Remarks
<i>DAY 3: Field survey of the references and field campaign management</i>	
<i>TIME</i>	ACTIVITY
9:00 – 9:30 am	Introduction of the reference sites
9:40 – 10:40 am	Protocols and tools
10:40 – 11:00 am	COFFEE BREAK
11:00 – 1:00 pm	Site selection, planning and organization
1:00 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH
1:45 – 3:30 pm	Field campaign planning and budgeting (hands-on)
3:30 – 4:15 pm	Unfinished business, Feedback, Closing Remarks
<i>DAY 4: FIELD VISIT</i>	
<i>TIME</i>	ACTIVITY
8:00 – 10:00 am	Travel to the Field Experimental Site
10:00 – 12:00	Demonstration of the SOP for the field survey
12:00 – 1:00 pm	LUNCH
1:00 – 3:00 pm	Demonstration of field survey protocols for the reference site
3:00 – 3:05 pm	Closing remarks
3:05 – 4:00 pm	Return trip
4.00 – 5.00pm	Quality control of the data collected this day in the field

ANNEX B: Protocol and standard operating procedure

The tasks to be performed at the Minimalistic Reference (MRS) sites

At each MRS site four (4) unit-volume composite samples should be collected. Two unit-volume composite samples representing the *surface* (0 – 5 cm) should be collected for 1.) pesticide residue and 2.) bulk density analysis. One unit-volume composite sample should be collected from the 3.) 20-50 (*subsoil*) and one unit-volume composite sample should be collected from the 4.) 0-20 cm (*topsoil*) depth interval for bulk density determination. Each sample should be a composite sample composed from three (3) subsamples collected from the soil surface, main and side walls of a mini pit that has to be excavated at the center of the sampling location. In case of favorable circumstances (eg.: non-present hard rock, plinthite, extreme compaction or cementation within the sampling depth) you need to have four (4) samples (2 *surface*, 1 *topsoil*, 1 *subsoil*) at each MRS Site.

Using the ODK Collect App for data recording

You need to follow the next steps to connect your ODKCollect app to the server established for the Reference Site activities:

1. Open the ODKCollect application
2. On the main screen select “Get Blank Form”
3. Select “Soils4Africa **Minimalistic** Reference Site description tool”
4. Click “Get Selected”
5. On the main screen select “Fill Blank Form”
6. Select “Soils4Africa **Minimalistic** Reference Site description tool”
7. You can start the data collection.

Main steps in the ODK form “Soils4Africa Minimalistic Reference Site description tool”

Entering general information

The mandatory fields are marked with a red *

1. Specification of the *unique identifier of the sampling location*. Note that you must enter the information in the given way. If you enter the information incorrectly the application will warn you and will not let you continue.
2. You need to select the date and time of the field work.
3. You need to specify the surveyor persons.
4. You need to record the coordinates of the sampling location.
5. Taking photos of the mini-profile:

The form will ask you to take or upload pictures on the mini-profile that you need to prepare for undisturbed sampling. Preferably you should take photos of the main and side walls of the mini-profile that you sample. If you would like to take or upload multiple images, you need to perform that one by one. After taking a photo, click “Next”, select “Add” and take the next photo. Repeat this procedure as many times as many photos you would like to take/upload. If you are ready with taking photos select “do not add” after clicking “Next”.

Record information on the sampling

You should provide information on the sampling of the *surface*, *topsoil* and *subsoil* as well.

If you haven’t been able to collect the sample (either surface or subsoil or topsoil, or neither of them) you should provide information on the restrictive conditions.

Scanning the QR code for the samples

If you have been able to collect the unit-volume samples, you should scan the QR code that is the unique identifier of the samples.

Be careful not to scan the same QR code for surface/topsoil/subsoil samples!

Generating QR codes for labelling of the unit-volume soil samples

The Country Supervisor will generate labels for the soil sample ID (UDSS-ID) for all unit-volume samples to be taken on the MRS sites within the country. The steps of the QR code generation are described in “Instruction manual for Country Supervisors”. The generation of the QR codes particularly for the MRS sites is the following:

- Visit the following homepage: <https://tag.qed.ai/sheet/>
- Leave all settings default except of:
- Margins Top: 5 mm, Bottom: 5 mm, Left: 10 mm; Right: 10 mm
- Length: 5
 - **Prefix:** u”country_code” (eg.: uDRC)
 - **No. of codes:** set a number that is ~20% higher than four times the number of the Minimalistic Reference sites in within the country (eg.: 36 sites – $4 \times 36 * 1.2 = 172,8$ set the No. of codes to 175)
 - Columns: 6 Rows: 8
 - Code padding: 1
 - Font size: 14

Figure 1.: Examples of QR codes for the undisturbed samples

For printing, laminating, protecting, cutting recommendations and requirements read the relevant section of the “Instruction Manual for Country Supervisors”.

Tools needed for taking the undisturbed samples on MRS sites

The following tools are needed for preparing the mini-pit and taking the undisturbed samples.:

1. A spade
2. A shovel
3. A hammer or a mallet
4. An undisturbed sampler tool (optional)
5. A block of wood to protect the metallic rings
6. Short and long knives
7. At least two metallic rings of 100 cm³ volume (seven rings are recommended)
8. A measuring tape.

Figure 2.: The tools needed on the MRS sites

Brief overview of the tasks to be performed on minimalistic Reference Sites

1. Delineate a $\sim 70 \times 90$ cm area on the soil surface, at the central point of the sampling location.
2. Take three unit-volume ($3 \times 100 \text{ cm}^3$) soil sub-samples from the *surface* (0 – 5 cm depth interval). Put the three soil cores into the same *surface* plastic bag to have a composite unit-volume *surface* sample (300 cm^3) for pesticide residue analysis.
3. Repeat step 2 to collect a composite unit-volume *surface* sample (300 cm^3) for *surface* bulk density analysis.
4. Prepare a 50 cm deep mini profile with clean, straight, vertical main and side walls at the center of the sampling location
5. Take three unit-volume ($3 \times 100 \text{ cm}^3$) soil sub-samples from the *subsoil* (20 – 50 cm depth interval). Put the soil cores into the same *subsoil* plastic bag to have a composite unit-volume *subsoil* sample (300 cm^3).
6. Take three unit-volume ($3 \times 100 \text{ cm}^3$) soil sub-samples from the *topsoil* (0 – 20 cm depth interval). Put the three soil cores into the same *topsoil* plastic bag to have a unit-volume *topsoil* sample (300 cm^3).
7. Record the required information in the ODK application (take photos, provide information on any obstacles influencing the success of the sampling).
8. Scan the barcodes of the surface, topsoil, and subsoil samples.

Important remarks for the undisturbed sampling

Do not attempt to collect the samples in situations when there is a risk to damage the metallic ring. Examples of these situations:

- Hard rock or large coarse fragment content

- Extreme compaction
- Extreme cementation
- Iron pan or plinthite

Detailed protocol for performing undisturbed sampling

The preparation procedure of the mini profile for the undisturbed sampling needs the use of shovel and spade. Thus, even the taking of the standard (baseline) samples at the MRS sites is recommended by using spade (watch the relevant instruction video and read the section 6.2.2 of the Protocols of Field Survey), because the further preparation steps needed for having a proper surface for undisturbed sampling is straightforward if an already opened (however not yet prepared) pit is available.

Note: the description below describes the protocol of undisturbed sampling when full undisturbed sampling toolkit (hammer/mallet, metallic ring(s) and sampler) is not, only a hammer and one or more metallic ring(s) are available.

Figure 3. The layout of the sampling location. The image on the left shows the procedure of surface sampling prior opening the “mini-profile”. The image of the right shows the procedure of taking the subsoil and topsoil samples from the main wall of the “mini-profile”.

Taking undisturbed *surface* samples for pesticide residue analysis and *surface* bulk density

The two unit-volume samples for the 1.) pesticide residue analysis and 2.) surface bulk density should be taken from 0 – 5 cm depth interval (*surface*). For the *surface* sampling the metallic rings used for the undisturbed sampling should be used. Each sample should be a composite sample composed from the three (3) subsamples collected from the soil *surface*.

1. Prepare the tools needed for the undisturbed sampling. You will need a *hammer/mallet*, *metallic ring(s)* with the volume of 100 cm³, and a *piece of wood* for protecting the ring.
2. Remove the vegetation residues, grass, and litter, if any, from the surface.
3. If you have at least six metallic rings you can arrange them in advance prior starting the sampling. Arrange them in 3 × 2 configuration (Figure 3.). The upper left, central right and lower left sample should be collected for pesticide residue analysis. The upper right, central left and lower right sample should be collected for bulk density analysis. You can do it in the other way around as well but be sure that samples collected from opposite sides will be put in the same bag.
4. Place the metallic ring on the soil surface, beveled edge parallel with the surface to collect the surface sample.
5. Gently press the ring into the soil with your palm if possible. Do not force it, if you are not able to push further inward, stop.

- Gently press the metallic ring into the soil with the help of the hammer. Use a block of wood to push the ring with the hammer to avoid compaction of the soil and protect the ring. Avoid pushing the ring in too far or the soil will compact.

Figure 4.: The procedure of cleaning the surface and hammering the metallic ring into the soil surface

- Make four cuts with a spade at 8-10 cm from the metallic ring. Avoid to stand/step where the ring is hammered. Extract the resulting clump of soil with the spade.

If the soil is too compacted or too loose, and you can not extract a clump, excavate the ring by using knives (see Figure 7.)!

- Excavate a little bit around the ring outside edge of the ring with a small, flat-bladed knife.
- Fully excavate the ring by using a longer, flat-bladed knife. Remove excess soil from the bottom of the ring and around the outside edge of the ring with the knife.
- Push the soil core into the plastic bag.
- Repeat these steps for all the remaining 5 points.
- At the end you should have the content of three metallic rings in one plastic bag. You should have 2 plastic bags containing 300 cm³ sample for pesticide residue analysis and 300 cm³ sample for bulk density analysis.**

Figure 5.: Extracting of the the ring

Figure 6.: The excavation of the ring and bagging

Figure 7. The extraction and excavation of the ring in case when the soil surface if compacted or too loose to be able to extract a clump

Preparation of the “mini-pits” for subsoil and topsoil sampling

1. Prepare the mini pit. The “mini” pit should be at least 50 cm deep, and wide enough to ensure the convenient sampling. Prepare the main wall of the “mini-pit”. It should be as flat as possible, and debris-free (Figure 9. right).
2. Put the measuring tape on the main wall to identify the sampling depths.
3. Take a photo in the ODK form showing the full profile (example photo can be seen on Figure8. right).

Figure 8.: the prepared main walls of the “mini-pit”. You should take a photo in the ODK form like this one.

Performing the sampling of the SUBSOIL

1. Place the metallic ring on the main wall, beveled edge parallel with the main wall centered at 35 cm depth to collect the undisturbed subsoil. Try to avoid roots and cracks.
2. Gently press the ring into the soil with your palm if possible. Do not force it, if you are not able to push further inward, stop.
3. Gently press the metallic ring into the soil with the help of the hammer. Use a block of wood to push the ring with the hammer to avoid compaction of the soil and protect the ring. Avoid pushing the ring in too far or the soil will compact.
4. Excavate a little bit around the ring outside edge of the ring with a small, flat-bladed knife (See the full procedure on).
5. Fully excavate the ring by using a longer, flat-bladed knife. Remove excess soil from the bottom of the ring and around the outside edge of the ring with the knife.
6. Push the soil core into the plastic bag.
7. Repeat these steps at the two side walls of the profile as well to have the three sub-samples.
8. At the end you should have the content of three metallic rings in one bag representing 300 cm³ subsoil material.

Figure 9.: First steps of pushing the metallic ring into the soil

Figure 10.: Hammering the metallic ring into the soil, and the excavation

Figure 11.: Full excavation and removing excess soil material

Performing the sampling of the TOPSOIL

1. Follow the protocols of sampling the subsoil (steps of 1 – 5) for taking the topsoil unit-volume sample. The sampling depth is preferably 10 cm.
2. Important note: if you took the subsoil sample from the left side of the “mini-profile”, take the topsoil sample from the right side of the “mini-profile”.

3. Put the soil core into the plastic bag.
4. Repeat these steps at the two side walls of the mini profile to have three sub-samples.
5. At the end you should have the content of three metallic rings in one bag representing 300 cm³ topsoil material.

Figure 12.: Taking the undisturbed topsoil sample.

Bagging and labelling the subsoil, topsoil, and surface samples

The samples should be bagged and labelled the same way as the standard samples are. The differences are: QR codes starting with “u” should be used and different labelling should be indicated on the outer bag.

The samples collected should be double bagged using a plastic bag as inner bag and a cloth/paper bag as outer bag. The QR code is put between the inner and outer bag (ensure the bar code is scanned before it is put in the bag).

The first step of labelling is done in the ODK form by scanning the barcode at the appropriate section of the form. After scanning, put the QR code between the outer and inner bag.

On the outer bag, write the sampling point ID, and indicate PR_SURFACE for pesticide residue analysis, BD_SURFACE for surface, BD_TOPSOIL for topsoil, BD_SUBSOIL for subsoil bulk density analysis. Write with permanent marker.

Figure 13.: The plastic bags containing the 400 cm³ soil samples, the QR codes that should be put into the cloth bag (left). The bagged, labelled surface, topsoil, and subsoil samples (right)

Final remarks

During the sampling keep the following questions in your mind:

Did I take a photo of the prepared, cleaned wall of the mini profile?

Did I put the three undisturbed subsoil sub-samples in the same plastic bag?

Did I put the three undisturbed topsoil sub-samples in the same plastic bag?

Did I put the three undisturbed surface samples for pesticide residue analysis in the same plastic bag?

Did I put the three undisturbed surface samples for surface bulk density analysis in the same plastic bag?

Do I have 4 bags per sampling site representing the surface (2), subsoil (1) and topsoil (1)?

ANNEX C: Report Training workshop in Nigeria (WAH)

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budget for Nigerian country supervisors protocol and standard operating procedure

Date: 28-29 March 2022

Venue: IITA-Ibadan

Attendance:

James Jayeoba (Nasarawa State University, Keffi)

Jibrin M. Jibrin (Bayero University Kano)

Funmi Ande (IAR&T, Ibadan)

Phanuel Ayuka (IITA-DIMU)

Caroline Owuso (IITA-DIMU)

Olabosun Obileye (IITA-DIMU)

Samuel Mesele (IITA-CCO Field campaign)

Jeroen Huising (IITA- CCO Field campaign)

Programme:

Monday 28 March	
General introduction to the S4A project and the field campaign (explanation on the sampling design the mask of agricultural land, etc.)	Jeroen Huising
Introduction and demonstration of the SDMT	Phanuel Ayuka
Demonstration of the Sampling Unit Validation as part of the SDMT	Phanuel Ayuka
Protocol Field Survey – SOP an ODK	Samuel Mesele
Instructions for field campaign management	Samuel Mesele
Incl. exercises – generating of bar codes	Samuel Mesele
Tuesday 29 March	
Planning and organising of the field campaign (updating on progress so far and esp. sampling point validation done))	Jeroen Huising
Budgeting for the field campaign	Jeroen Huising
Onboarding of the CS to the SDMT and exercising	Phanuel Ayuka
Onboarding to the ONA platform and exercising with the ODK form	Phanuel Ayuka
Closing	Jeroen Huising

Purpose of the workshop and meeting:

We have reached quite far with the development of the Survey Data Management Tool and even though it has not yet been completed we had scheduled this week for testing of the tool. This also in view of the upcoming workshop planned for Ghana and Burkina Faso. For this purpose, the developers had come over

from Kenya. Rather than testing it ourselves, who had been closely involved with the development of the tool, we wanted to expose the tool to the country coordinators of Nigeria who had not been involved at all and for whom the tool is intended in the end. At the same time we wanted to take this opportunity to meet face to face for the first time and discuss the planning and budgeting for the field campaign and get their feedback on the possibilities for the implementation of the field campaign in Nigeria.

Outcome and conclusions:

1. The SDMT was demonstrated to the CSs and they are quite impressed with the design and user interface and they see this as a great innovation that can be of much use for other programs being undertaken in Nigeria, like the soil mapping program that has been initiated recently in Nigeria.
2. Useful comments were made on the SDMT itself that the developers will take onboard and to make required changes, like that it should be possible to extract coordinate and other data from the sampling point during the sampling point validation (rather than only being able to select in on-screen; no of PSU is not indicated in the dashboard at the job assignment screen; Quality Control should be possible for all the sampling points within a job at the same time, rather than one-by-one (point).
3. The country supervisors already reviewed and validated sampling points for safe and unsafe areas. Note that the number of sampling points assigned to Nigeria (479) includes safe and unsafe areas, which was done because some parts of the area officially recognised as unsafe can still be visited and we do have people on the ground. It therefore required local expertise to determine which locations are no-go areas. The CSs, based on the input from local persons and contacts have rejected 89 points remaining with 390 PSU in safe areas.
4. The CSs still need to complete the sampling point validation exercise considering additional criteria specified by the SDMT (e.g., restricted access, inaccessible area, incompatible land use types). A further reduction in the number of acceptable points is therefore expected.
5. If the rejection of the sampling points, without considering replacement by backup points, there are likely implications for the sampling design in that the proportionality of the number of sampling point in relation to the area the various land use category occupy is affected (there is a bias towards certain land use categories in the points being rejected). This needs to be discussed and possible action taken if considered undesirable.
6. All the country supervisors were all boarded onto the SDMT and can now further practice with it.
7. The way the field campaign is organised in Nigeria deviates somewhat from the model implemented in SDMT. That is, there will be field supervisors that will manage several survey teams. Rather than adding another role/user level in the SDMT these field supervisors are considered surveyors and the teams or the enumerators in the field will have to use the surveyor's username for registering on the platform to get the form and uploading the form once it is filled onto the platform. The enumerator should still be able to fill his/her name in the form such that he/she can be properly identified (the enumerator will use the surveyor's login details)
8. We presented the hardcopy of the protocols and SOP to them with illustrations and practical sessions on how to manage the field campaign at country level.

9. The Nigerian team resolved that the field campaign can be conducted within time window available for this year, if the total number of PSU is not more than the 390 that resulted after provisional validation of the proposed sapling points and provided that the field campaign can start in June 2022.
10. The Nigerian team estimated the cost for the field campaign, based on the same assumptions that underlie the planning of the field campaign: 390 PSU to be surveyed. It is concluded currently available budget, the calculation of which is based on the originally assigned 479 PSUs being surveyed, will fall short off the projected costs for the field campaign by \$15,144.
11. The request is made to keep and store soil samples in Nigeria for use by students but also for possible integration in national programmes. BUK has excellent facilities for storage of soil samples and has very good lab facilities, including a MIR spectrometer (as well as NIR spectrometer). It is considered a very valuable addition to their existing archive
12. For the field survey activities in Nigeria, the contract will be with the Nasarawa State University, Keffi, who will be responsible for managing the funds including disbursement to other in-country supervisors.
13. Soil samples will be aggregated at two locations within Nigeria: one is BUK-Centre for Dryland Agriculture and the other is either IITA or IAR&T in Ibadan.
14. No further discussions were held on the reference sites, and we will as soon as possible organise a meeting (online) with Erika and Adam to discuss the options for surveying reference sites in Nigeria
15. All country supervisors should have access to the project documents (for example documents on the sampling design) and this needs to be arranged soonest (whether online access via the website, or access to the project S4A Teams folder

Ad 9) The planning

For the field campaign Nigeria is split up in three regions, each being supervised by a country supervisor. The Northeast and Northwest will be supervised by Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin; The North-Central, Southeast and two states in the northeast by Prof. James Jayeoba; the Southwest, South-South and Kara state of the North-Central will be supervised by Prof Funmi Ande. The planning is summarized in the tables below

Region: North-central-SE&NE(two states)	
Planning and budgeting field survey NIGERIA	
	Number of PSU (before validation) 176
A	Number of PSU (after validation) 154
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations) 616
C	Number of samples to be taken 1232
D	Number of samples for prep&ship 924
E	Nr kg to be shipped 88
F	Total number of days field survey 154
	Number of teams conducting field survey 14

No of days in the field per team	11
No of teams per months in the field	3.5

The total number of days to be spend in the field is estimated at 154, based on the assumption that on average one PSU can be surveyed by one team in a day. We assume to have 14 teams in the field and do not expect any problem in establishing these teams. This means that on average a team will spend 11 days in the field. The window of opportunity for conducting the survey is from June to September; that is 4 months. This implies that, if we spread the survey over the full duration of the 4 months of the window of opportunity, we will have on average 3.5 teams working simultaneously within a month (which still allows for some spreading of the activities). And this is considered manageable.

Region: Northeast and Northwest

Planning and budgeting field campaign

A	Number of PSU	173
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations)	692
C	Number of samples to be taken	1384
D	Number of samples for prep&ship	1038
E	Nr kg to be shipped	99
F	Total number of days field survey	173
	Number of teams conducting field survey	8
	Number of field days per team	22
	Number of teams in the field per month	2

For the NE and NW region we have 173 PSUs to be surveyed (after validation). The time window for conducting the field campaign is likewise 4 months (from June to September). The number of teams they want to deploy is 8, in which case on average one team will do 22 days in the field. That is in practice a full month. Number of teams working simultaneously is 2, which can be very well managed.

Section: SW-SS-NC(1 state:Kwara)

Planning and budgeting for the subregion

CS: Funmi Ande

A	Number of PSU (after validation)	63
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations)	252
C	Number of samples to be taken	504
D	Number of samples for prep&ship	378
E	Nr kg to be shipped	36
F	Total number of days field survey	63
	Number of teams conducting field survey	5
	Number of days in the field per team	13

Number of teams in the field per month 1

The South-South and Southwest region is the smaller region and will have 63 PSUs to be surveyed. If we employ 5 teams it means that one team is projected to be 13 working days in the field. For window of opportunity to conduct the survey of 5 months (June -October) we can have the teams deployed consecutively with one team operating each month.

Conclusion is that Nigeria plans to have the survey completed still in 2022.

Ad 10) Budgeting

The budget available for a sampling location is provided in the table below. WE will go by scenario 2 which gives a more realistic assessment of the cost for the training workshops to be held in each region.

Budget for field campaign at pan-African level (WP4)

	€	Scenario1 (\$)	Scenario 2 (\$)
Toal budget available	1440000	1,627,200	1,627,200
Cost for shipping samples to RSA		107,395	107,395
Cost training workshops		68,342	130,000
Cost reference sites		45,562	45,562
Budget available for survey in countries		1,405,901	1,344,243
Budget per sampling location		68.33	65.33

The cost per sampling point is calculated by dividing the budget that is available for the field survey by the number of sampling points projected by the sampling design: 20576. It results in \$65.33 per sampling point, which is then used to calculate the budget available to the country based on the number of sampling points allocated for that country.

For Nigeria the budget available is calculated based on the 476 PSU that are located within the territory of Nigeria.

Budget available (based on \$65.33 per sampling point location)	\$125,172
Overhead charge Nassarawa State University (5%)	\$6,259
Net available	\$118,914

The budget available for each PSU, on average is indicated in the table below

	Scenario 2
Total budget avail survey	\$118,914
Cost sample preparation	\$9,360
Cost shipment samples internal	\$2,223

Cost fee country supervisors	\$15,600
Available budget field survey	\$91,731
Avr bgt available per team	
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$235.21

The fee for the country supervisors is based on the assumption that 20% of the time needed for the survey in the field is spent on supervision and coordination. We calculated a daily fee of \$200 for the country supervisor. The fee for the country supervisor in case of Nigeria has to be divided between the three country supervisors and they have declared this amount to be acceptable. Subsequently the cost for doing one PSU, or for having a team in the field for one day is estimated as follows:

Budget available for one PSU (₦)	₦ 97,846.40
Daily Allowance - Team leader	30,000
Daily Allowance - Team Members	30,000
Transport:	
Location	25000
Motorcycle	7000
Security/ Local Guide	12,000
Material and Logistics	10,000
Total cost one PSU	114,000
Shortfall for one PSU	-₦ 16,153.60
Total shortfall (nr days/PSU*daily shortfall)	-₦ 6,299,904.00
Total Shortfall campaign in \$	-\$15,144

The budget available per PSU or a team one day in the field is calculated by using an exchange rate of ₦416 to the USD (official exchange rate). The total shortfall is calculated by multiplying the shortfall for one PSU by 390, which is the number of PSUs after validation. Note the shortfall is estimated at USD fifteen million even though the number of sampling units has already been reduced by approximately 20%.

Ad 11) Storage facility a BUK

BUK, Kano, has very good storage facilities for soil samples.
Please, see a picture above

ANNEX D: Report Training workshop in Ghana (WAH)

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budget for English speaking countries WAH

Date: 4- 7 April 2022

Venue: SRI, Kumasi, Ghana

Attendance:

Mustapha Abdulkadir (PhD student, Nigeria)

Mr Kwaku Armooh (SRI, Ghana)

Michael Asuboa (SRI, Ghana)

Abdul Rahman Conteh (CS, Sierra Leone)

Adam Csorba (Resource person reference sites, MATE, Hungary)

Padlass Edeator (SRI, Ghana)

Yanquoi Harris (CS, Liberia)

Jeroen Huising (WP4 coordinator, IITA)

Abdou Rahman Jobe (CS, Gambia)

Caleb Melenya (Post Doc, SRI, Ghana)

Samuel Mesele (WP4, IITA)

Mamoudou Traore (Coordinator of the West Africa Hub)

Stephen Owusu (SRI, Ghana)

Edward Yeboah (CS, SRI, Ghana)

Programme

ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
Monday April 4th, 2022		
Welcome and Introduction of participants	Kwaku Armooh; Padlass Edeator	
Welcome by Director CSIR-SRI	Edward Yeboah	
Purpose, objectives and expected results of the training workshop	Jeroen Huising	
Protocol for the field survey	Samuel Mesele	
Protocol for field survey	Samuel Mesele	
Protocol for field campaign management	Jeroen Huising	
Field campaign management: planning and budgeting	Jeroen Huising	Largely deferred to day 2

Financial and contractual arrangements	Jeroen Huising	Deferred to day 2
Discussion, feedback and remarks	Jeroen Huising	
Closing Remarks	Edward Yeboah	

ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
Tuesday April 5th, 2022		
Opening day 2 and recap day 1	Edward Yeboah	
The use of online survey data and management tool (SDMT)	Jeroen Huising; Sam Mesele	
Registration/ onboarding to the SDMT	Jeroen Huising; Sam Mesele	
Introduction to the SOP and ODK forms	Samuel Mesele	
Registration on ONA platform; hands-on experience use of the ODK forms	Samuel Mesele	
Review of sampling design for the individual countries	Jeroen Huising	
Validation of the sampling point locations	Sam Mesele; Jeroen Huising	brought forward to day 1
Planning and budgeting for field campaign at country level	Group work	Procurements, sample preparation, shipment
Closing Remarks	Dr Edward Yeboah	

ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
Wednesday April 6th 2022		
Introduction of the reference sites	Adam Csorba	
Protocols and tools	Ádám Csorba	
Site selection, planning and organization	Adam Csorba	
COVID-19 testing for return flight	Stephan Owusu	
Financial settlement (per diems, reimbursement for covid testing, and other)	Jeroen Huising	
Any unfinished business	Ádám Csorba Jeroen Huising Samuel Mesele	
Closing Remarks	Edward Yeboah	

ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
Thursday, April 7, 2022		
Travel to the Field Experimental Site	Michael Asuboa	

Demonstration of the SOP for the field survey	Samuel Mesele	One sampling point done, only
Demonstration field survey protocol for the reference site: mini pints and sample taking for BD measurement; profile description using FAO protocols and form	Ádám Csorba	
Return trip	Michael Asuboa	
Concluding administrative arrangements	Edward Yeboah	

Purpose of the workshop and meeting:

The purpose for this workshop was to introduce and explain the protocol for the field survey and the instructions for the country supervisor how to manage the field campaign, to train country supervisor on the use of tools such that they can also instruct their surveyors on how to use the tools and to conduct a planning and budgeting exercise such that they can develop their own country budget. The tools are, as yet, available within a test environment and will be transferred to a production platform once the tools have been fully developed. It means that the URL where to access the tools will change only and should not present any problem to the CS. That is also true for the tools and the support materials like the instruction video that will be available online. For explaining the protocol for the field survey, use is made of the online available video instruction materials. We assisted participants in creating their account on the ONA platform and provided them access to the Soils4Africa ODK forms such that they could get hands-on experience while the ODK form was explained. Country Supervisors were onboarded to the SDMT in the role as CS such that they could practice with and view the data for their country while we explained the functioning of the SDMT. In this manner the CS could practice with the validation of the sampling points using data from their own country. We guided them through the generation of QR codes and at the same time the CS generated the QR codes for their own country. For the planning and budgeting we provided the participants with a template such that they could work on the planning and budgeting of the campaign for their own country, while the planning and budgeting was explained using Ghana as an example. The situation for each of the countries was reviewed. Country supervisors were given a week to reflect on the results so far and to present a budget by the end of the following week.

The field day is intended to exercise with the navigation in the field, demonstrate and practice implementing the protocol for the field survey. We also had a soil pit dug for demonstrating soil profile description and at the same time getting the practical experience with the time needed and cost involved with digging a soil pit.

For us as developers of the protocols and tools, and as managers and coordinators of the field campaign the purpose for the workshop is also to assess the capacity and skills of the country supervisors, both to using these tools as well as with doing this kind of field work (including navigating in the field) in order to determine the need for further support.

Outcome and conclusions:

1. The participants were quite happy with the protocols and instruction manual and express to have gained deep understanding of what the surveyors and country supervisors need to do. No adjustments required for the protocol for the field survey and the instructions for the country supervisor.
2. Booklets (size A5) of the Protocol for Field Survey, Protocol for Field Survey Management and Standard Operating Procedures for Sample Collection and Field Observations have been distributed to all participants. (Field Survey Management Annex F, screen dump for the QR code generation needs to be revised)
3. The CSs generated the QR codes for their countries.
4. Notes on the SDMT tool:
 - a. At regional level in the dashboard – The number of PSU are not correct; needs to be checked
 - b. There seems to be problem with the use of the SDMT when the internet connection is not strong – Needs to be investigated
 - c. It is seen as a shortcoming that the identifier of the PSU is not displayed; suggested to let the PSU-ID pops up when hovering above the locator
 - d. Should be possible to reject/delete a job once it is assigned (to reassign and correct for errors if needed)
 - e. Number of PSUs should be listed in job assignment
 - f. Once assigned as surveyor, you cannot assign the same person as a country supervisor. It requires you to use a second email address. You cannot also not change their role. We need to check whether that also applies for CS and Hub Coordinator. We need to think whether we want to make the adjustments to make that possible (not sure whether we want the CS to be a surveyor at the same time).
5. Time windows for the field survey for the four countries has been specified:
 - a. Ghana: July to November (4 months);
 - b. Sierra Leone: May, June, Oct, Nov, (Dec) – 4 months.
 - c. Liberia: May – July, Nov (4 months);
 - d. Gambia: May, June, Oct, Nov (4 month).
6. Notes on the SOP and ODK form for the field survey:
 - a. For entering slope position make distinction between flat and almost flat terrain and to undulating and mountainous terrain. Or otherwise, if only one value list is used clearly state that there are different options for both landforms.
 - b. Stoniness coarse surface fragments): Consider applying this only in case of coarse gravel (2-6cm), stones (6-20cm), Boulders (20-60cm) and large boulders (60-200cm). The size class should be indicated as well
7. Reference sites: For the West Africa region about 70 reference sites will be selected. These will be selected along two transects – running south to north. One transects will be in Ghana – Burkina Faso, the other in Nigeria.

8. The team doing the reference site should also do the standard sampling points within the PSU, for increasing efficiency. For this purpose, it is suggested that the surveyor of the reference sites should be part of the regular survey teams. That will be difficult to organise and coordinate. So, we will leave this to Caleb and Mustapha to organise themselves. Should be discusses with the CS such that the particular PSUs are not part of the job assignment.
9. We observed that navigating in the field using MAPS.ME works much better than using a GPS. Maps.me show roads and tracks to a high level of detail, which is not available on the GPS. The accuracy of Maps.me in locating the point was the same as the GPS. We will recommend all teams to use MAPS.ME
10. Suggested to change the protocol for the 'minimalistic' reference sites – with respect to the mini pits.
 - a. Consider including taking undisturbed samples of 0-5cm from the topsoil for pesticide residue measurements- To be discussed with Vera ☐ adjust protocol
 - b. Consider doing profile description for the mini pits, at least for the A-horizon and the horizon directly below. For this purpose, the mini pit could be 1m wide of which one half is used for taking the undisturbed samples and the other half for describing the profile. Need to think about possible implications for taking the undisturbed samples (e.g., 0-5 cm, 10-20 cm, 20-50 cm)
11. It is observed that the participants, especially the CS and somewhat older people, have difficulty creating accounts where needed, downloading, and installing the tools as well as with using the tools (they are not fully computer literate). It means that they will need some continued support and close supervision of the hub coordinator. Ghana needs to be prepared to provide that support.
12. Budgeting has been done for all countries during the training workshop. Ghana was used as an example. The results for Ghana will quite accurate. The other countries were given a week to reflect on the tentative outcome and to present a final budget within a week. Only Sierra Leone has complied. They did not use the right template though, illustrating the difficulty having with understanding and using the XLS template. The Ghana budget showed a deficit of in total \$16,213. The budget for Sierra Leone show a deficit of \$6,240, but needs to be reviewed still.

Ad 11) Planning and budgeting for the Ghana field campaign.

The tentative figures for the planning of the field campaign in Ghana are presented in the Table 1 below. Ghana intends to deploy 5 field teams. They have 109 PSU to survey and expect to be able to do one PSU per day, considering the distances to travel to reach the location of the PSU. The survey needs to be conducted in 4 months (the window of opportunity to conduct the survey). That means that each team on average will spend 22 days in the field, which seems a bit much. IF they spread out the field campaign over the 4 months available, there will be an overlap in the period the teams are in the field. The number of teams in the field per month is 1.25 meaning that at some times they will have 2 teams operating in the field at the same time, which can be quite well coordinated

Table 1. Planning figures for the field campaign Ghana

	Country/Section:	Ghana
	Country Supervisor:	Edward Yeboah
	Number of PSUs original (in sampling design)	109
A	Number of PSU (after validation)	109
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations)	436
C	Number of samples to be taken	872
D	Number of samples for prep&ship	872
E	Nr kg to be shipped	436
F	Total number of days field survey	109
	Number of teams conducting field survey	5
	Number of days in the field per team	22
	Number of teams in the field per month	1.25

The cost for shipment of soil samples within the country (and the region) is estimated at \$10 per kg (see Table 2. That is probably a bit much for Ghana per se, but the practice will show. The daily fee for the country supervisor is set at US\$150, which is relatively modest.

Table 2. Key figures for planning and budgeting field campaign

Key figures & reference data

Number of TSU per PSU	4
BGT avail per Sampling location (€)	€ 72
BGT avail per Sampling location (\$)	\$85
Number of samples per location	2
weight sample for wet chem (g)	500
weight sample for spectral (g)	500
Percentage samples for wet chem	15%
Percentage samples for spectral	85%
Cost shipment per kg (within country and region, \$)	\$10
Cost sample preparation (\$)	\$3
Average time for survey PSU (days)	1
Percentage time allocation CS of time for field survey (days)	20%
Daily fee country supervisor (\$)	\$150
Window of operation (month)	4
Exchange rate \$/local currency	7.45

The budget available for the field campaign in Ghana is determined by the number of sampling points times the amount calculated to be available per sampling point. Deducted is the overhead charges for the executing agency. That is Soil Research Institute in this case, of which Edward Yeboah is the executing director.

Table 3. Budget available for field campaign and per Primary Sampling Unit

Budget available per sampling point (\$)	65.33	
Overall budget available for campaign for the country (\$)	28,484	
Overhead charges executing agency (%)	10.00%	
Net budget available for the campaign (\$)	25,635	
Total budget avail survey	\$25,635	
Cost sample preparation	\$2,616	
Cost shipment samples	\$4,360	
Cost fee country supervisor	\$3,270	
Available budget field survey	\$15,389	
Avr bgt available per team	\$3,078	
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$141.19	
Available budget field team per day in the field (Ghana Cedis)	GHC 1,052	
Daily Allowance - Team leader	GHC 350.00	
Daily Allowance - Team Members	GHC 310.00	
Transport:		
Location	GHC 1,000.00	
Motorcycle	GHC 300.00	
Security/ Local Guide	GHC 100.00	
Material and Logistics	GHC 100.00	
Estimated cost team one day in the field	GHC 2,160.00	
Balance avail bgt and estimated cost	-GHC 1,108.15	
Total shortfall \$	-	16,213

The budget available per team per day is calculated based on the assumption of one PSU being surveyed per day and the budget available per PSU. Looking at the estimated cost per day for a team operating in the field we see that there is a shortfall of GHC 1,108.15 per day or per PSU. Multiplying with the total number of PSU, gives a total shortfall of US\$ 16,213. We need to find solutions how to compensate Ghana for the extra expenses.

ANNEX E: Report Training workshop in Burkina Faso (WAH)

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budget for French speaking countries WAH

Date: 11-14 April 2022 at Royal Beach Hotel, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso

Attendance:

Codjo Emile Agbangba (CS, University of Abomey-Calavi, Benin)

Marcelino Mutna Brimbandé (CS, Labo National des Sols, Guinea-Bissau) Tiémakan

Diakité (CS, IER LaboSEP, Mali)

Aïssatou Taran Diallo (CS, Guinée) Bélo

Hema (DEP, BUNASOLS, BF)

Jeroen Huising (WP4 coordinator, IITA)

Désiré Kabore (GIS, BUNASOLS, BF) Etienne

Kabore (BUNASOLS, BF) Saidou Addam

Kiari (CS, INRA, Niger) Johan Leenaars

(ISRIC, Netherlands)

Etienne Blaise M'Boumba (CS, Ecole Supérieure d'Agronomy, Togo)

Samuel Mesele (WP4, IITA) Moussa

Nikiena (BUNASOLS, BF)

Inouso Ouedraogo (BUNASOLS, BF)

Rasmané Romba (BUNASOLS, BF) Adama

Sawadogo (CS, BUNASOLS, BF) Seancon Silga

(BUNASOLS, BF)

Mamoudou Traore (Coordinator of the West Africa Hub) Demeango

Serge Zon (dep. CS, UNA, Côte d'Ivoire)

Mamadou Ousseynou Ly, the representative of Senegal, was absent with apologies. He was not able to catch his flight for reasons beyond his control.

Programme

Lundi 11 avril 2022 : Campagne terrain		
ACTIVITES	RESPONSIBILITES	OBSERVATION
Accueil et enregistrement	Secrétaire & PRM	
Accueil et présentation des superviseurs pays et des facilitateurs	Mamoudou TRAORE	Mamoudou was absent with apologies, task assumed by Belo Hema
Allocution SG MARAH	DEP & DG SG MARAH	
Présentation du but, des objectifs et des résultats attendus du programme de formation	Jeroen Huising	
Protocole pour l'enquête de terrain	Samuel Mesele, Johan Leenaars	

Protocole de gestion de campagne terrain	Jeroen Huising	
Gestion des campagnes terrain : planification et budgétisation	Jeroen Huising Mamoudou Traoré	Deferred to Wednesday
Dispositions financières et contractuelles	Jeroen Huising Mamoudou Traoré	Deferred to Wednesday
Discussion, retours et remarques	Jeroen Huising	
Synthèse et fin de la journée	Mamoudou Traoré	

Mardi 12 avril 2022 : Enquête de terrain : outils et techniques		
ACTIVITES	RESPONBILITES	OBSERVATION
L'utilisation des données d'enquête en ligne et de l'outil de gestion de gestion des données d'enquête (OGDT)	Jeroen Huising Samuel Mesele	
Introduction aux formulaires de procédure opérationnelle standard (POS) et Trousse de Données Ouvertes (TDO)	Johan Leenaars Samuel Mesele	
Validation des emplacements des points de prélèvement	Travaux de groupe	
Synthèse et fin de la journée	Mamoudou Traoré	

Mercredi 13 avril 2022 : Enquête de terrain sur les sites de référence		
ACTIVITES	RESPONBILITES	OBSERVATION
Examen du plan d'échantillonnage pour les différents pays	Jeroen Huising	
Campagnes terrain : budgétisation	Jeroen Huising	
Dispositions financières et contractuelles	Dr Jeroen Huising Dr Mamoudou Traoré	
Païement des per diem et remboursement des tests COVID	Jeroen Huising	
Test COVID-19 - prélèvement d'échantillons	Mamoudou Traore	
Visite au BUREAU NATIONAL DES SOLS	Equipe BUNASOLS ; DEP & DLA	

Jeudi 14 avril 2022 : SORTIE DE TERRAIN		
ACTIVITES	RESPONBILITES	OBSERVATION
Voyage au site expérimental sur le terrain	Equipe BUNASOLS, Désiré KABORE ; Sécurité et santé : DRH	
Démonstration de la procédure opérationnelle standard (POS) pour l'enquête sur le terrain	Dr Johan Leenaars Dr Samuel Mesele	
Organisation des voyages retour	Equipe BUNASOLS	

Purpose and objective of the training workshop

The purpose and objective of this training workshop was the same as the previous workshop in Ghana, namely, to explain the protocol for the field survey and the instructions for the management of the field campaign, to train the participant on the use of the various tools and apps that are used for this purpose and to help the country supervisors in the planning and budgeting for the field campaign in their respective countries. With respect to the planning and budgeting we want to get an idea of the feasibility of conducting the field campaign, whether the countries have the capacity to conduct the field campaign within the time frame indicated and to get a clear idea of the budgetary challenges for conducting the campaign. All with the aim to prepare the country supervisor well for the task of initiating and coordinating the campaign within their countries and to make sure the campaign can start in time, by June this year.

The group was larger than the group of participants of the previous workshops, the workshop had to be conducted in French, and quite a few participants had difficulty in understanding how the various tools worked and in using the tools. Some participants were less computer literate. Because of this the various sessions took considerably more time than anticipated and we had to skip all sessions related to the reference sites. We do not consider this to be of any consequence but emphasises the need to take the organisation of the survey of the reference sites in our own hands and organise this outside the scope of this training workshop.

We distributed the booklets in French on the protocol for the field survey (“Protocole d’enquête sur le terrain”) and the instructions for the field survey management (“Protocole pour le gestion des enquêtes sur le terrain”), which helped a lot, and we had the assistance of Johan Leenaars for the translation in French when needed.

We had separate sessions with Johan Leenaars to implement changes to the ODK form for the field survey that had been earlier discussed. These changes were implemented before presenting the SOP and ODK form to the group, which allowed us to directly test the changes made.

The participants, and BUNASOLS especially, expressed their appreciation for the training they had received. We thank BUNASOLS for hosting this event and the local organisation.

Outcome and conclusions:

1. The participants were very satisfied with the training workshop. Some had extreme difficulty in following instruction and were also not able to complete all the exercises. This refers to the use of the SDMT, generation of the QR codes, signing on to the ONA platform downloading and filling the ODK form as well as using the template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign and concluding the budget for their own country survey. This implies that BUNASOLS need to provide additional support for some countries (e.g., Guinee, Guinee Bissau, and Mali and Niger to some extent, but even for BUNASOLS themselves requires attention) but also that the country supervisors organize the support of younger colleagues that are more computer literate.
2. Booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey, Protocol for Field Survey Management were provided in French translation. We observed that we need to check on the French translation. Translations for *life form* and *mottles* were not readily understood for example (did not represent a common expression in French). The ODK

and SOP are only available in English still. WE will need the ODK form in French and herewith also

the SOP in French.

3. Countries have been asking for the data on the SSU and TSU for their respective countries. We have provided Désiré Kabore with all the data in relation to the West Africa Hub and he (BUNASOLS) will be responsible for distributing the data to the various countries when requested. (It is the role of the RHC)
4. Notes with respect to the survey protocol, ODK form and SOP:
 - a. Knife should be included in the materials required for mixing the soil, rather than using your hands
 - b. Check and correct translation in French: 'mottles' is 'taches'; Life form can best be translated with "structure et forme des plantes"
 - c. ODK form needs to be translated in French and needs to be properly checked
 - d. Drainage class needs to be restored as section in the form and needs to indicate the visible signs in the label or description
 - e. Life form was deleted from the form and needs to be put back.
 - f. Put 'measures' back to be indicated for the conservation measures. What is there now does not work for the category of structural measures
 - g. Put a constraint on the length of the SP-ID to be filled (for validation)
5. Participant expressed the wish to be able to use the tools for their own purpose as well. For the ODK that should not be a problem since they have access to the form and are able to make changes. For the SDMT that is more difficult. The structure can be adopted and DIMU will be happy to provide support to develop tools that is tuned to their own needs.
6. Time was considered too short, and we promised to follow up with ZOOM or MS-TEAMS meetings to explain specific aspects of the various tools when needed. The CSs need to express their needs in that respect.
7. Whether the contract for the execution for the field campaign is with the organization or with the individual was discussed. The OH charges levied for their own organization seems to be higher than what is mentioned in the previous workshops. Individual contracts seem to be possible while the person still works for his/her organization and used the resources. We will need to investigate the possibilities and the possible consequences (whether you can hold the person still accountable).
8. The attitude in the French-speaking countries seems a bit different from the English-speaking countries. The demands or expectations for the daily fees of the country supervisors are considerably higher than what was mentioned in the previous workshop for the English-speaking countries. And they do not seem to realize that this is at the expense of the funds available for the field campaign itself. Also, the request for laptops, smartphones and GPS devices are quite high. We have tried to instill the notion that the field campaign should be organized in the most cost-effective manner and that the CS should explore cost saving measures.
9. We have received the tentative planning and budget documents for 7 countries of the WAH. The data for Guinee and Guinee Bissau are missing still. We have yet to review the budget provided and we are likely still far off from a final contractual agreement. During the meeting the agreement that BUNASOLS will fund the field campaign within their own

country from the budget they have available for the regional coordination. We have also provided the other countries with the budget available to them for the field campaign when the funds freed up is distributed over the remaining countries *pro rata* their number of PSUs. We will probably need to inform the EU of this change in the budget (or change in for which the budget for regional coordination is being used). The other countries applauded BUNASOLS for this gesture, even though it will not fully resolve the financial issues.

10. We found only shallow laterite soils during the field visit (an existing and valid sampling point). In Burkina as well as in the other countries of the WAH, especially the Sahel (Guinea savanna) region, you find a lot of these shallow laterite soils. The time needed for such a point is much reduced, implying that it should be possible to do more than one PSU a day on average.
11. BUNASOLS has good storage facilities for soil samples and it seems well organized. Further the lab is well prepared for doing the sample preparation. They have a well- equipped lab but lack an infrared spectrometer.

Ad 9) Planning and budget calculation as done during the training workshop.

The budgeting for the field campaign is fictive, in the sense that BF has agreed to pay for the field campaign from the budget for regional coordination, but therefore still relevant in terms of the sacrifice they are making, for which we are extremely grateful.

BUNASOLS expects to be able to send 13 teams to the field for the survey. Considering that they have 127 PSU to survey and assuming that a team will need one day on average to survey one PSU, each team will spend 10 days in the field on average. Considering that the window of opportunity is 4 months, Burkina will have 3 to 4 teams operating at the same time in the field, which put a high demand on the coordination.

Table 1. Data for the planning of the field campaign

	Country/Section:	Burkina Faso
	Country Supervisor:	Adama Sawadogo
	Number of PSUs original (in sampling design)	127
A	Number of PSU (after validation)	127
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations)	508
C	Number of samples to be taken	1016
D	Number of samples for prep&ship	762
E	Nr kg to be shipped	508
F	Total number of days field survey	127
	Number of teams conducting field survey	13
	Number of days in the field per team	10
	Number of teams in the field per month	3.25

In Table 2 the reference data is provided. Cost for shipment internally within the country is set at US\$0.50 per kg. Cost for sample preparation is relatively high. The daily fee for the

country supervisor is set at US\$ 500 per day. This is high and has been reduced to US\$250 in a later version.

Table 2. Key figures and reference data

Number of TSU per PSU	4
BGT avail per Sampling location (€)	€ 72
BGT avail per Sampling location (\$)	\$85
Number of samples per location	2
weight sample for wet chem (g)	350
weight sample for spectral (g)	50
Percentage samples for wet chem	15%
Percentage samples for spectral	85%
Cost shipment per kg (within country and region, \$)	\$0.50
Cost sample preparation (\$)	\$5
Average time for survey PSU (days)	1
Percentage time allocation CS of time for field survey (days)	30%
Daily fee country supervisor (\$)	\$500
Window of operation (month)	4
Exchange rate local currency/US\$	600

New in table 3, compared to earlier budget calculations, is that cost for the capacity building of the surveyors is included, which is a realistic assumption given the experience from this workshop. The fee for the country supervisor is relatively high and which results in a very low budget for the survey of one PSU and consequently very low budget per individual sampling point.

Table 3. Budget available for the field campaign and per PSU

Budget available per sampling point (\$)	65.33
Overall budget available for campaign for the country	\$33,188
Overhead charges executing agency (%)	10.00%
Net budget available for the campaign	\$29,869
Total budget avail survey	\$29,869
Cost sample preparation	\$5,080
Cost shipment samples	\$254
Renforcement de capacite	\$5,000
Cost fee country supervisor	\$19,050
Available budget field survey	\$5,485
Avr bgt available per team	\$422
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$43.19
Budget per sampling point	\$10.80

The cost for team operating in the field for one day is specified below, specified in CFA. Considering the budget available per PSU (see table 3) it shows a shortfall of **-159,087 F CFA** per day in the field, which amounts to a shortfall of **20,204,074 F CFA** for the whole campaign and which is equivalent to **US\$ 33,673.46**.

Table 4. Cost estimate team operating one day in the field and estimated budget shortfall

Available budget field team per day in the field (local curr.)	25,913 F CFA
Daily Allowance - Team leader	50,000 F CFA
Daily Allowance - Team Members	40,000 F CFA
Transport:	
Location	60,000 F CFA
Motorcycle	15,000 F CFA
Security/ Local Guide	15,000 F CFA
Material and Logistics	5,000 F CFA
Estimated cost team one day in the field	185,000 F CFA
Balance avail bgt and estimated cost	-159,087 F CFA
Total campaign	-20,204,074 F CFA

Ad 11) Facility for storage of soil samples at BUNASOLS

ANNEX F: Report Training workshop in South Africa (SAH)

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budget FOR South Africa region

Date: 7-10 June 2022

Venue: Stellenbosch University, Department of Soil Science, Lombardi building, Stellenbosch, RSA

Attendance:

Momade Mamudo Ibraimo	Mozambique
Marina Coetzee	Namibia
Stalin Sichinga	Zambia
Patrick Dlamini	eSwatini
Polao Moepi	Lesotho
Peter Eze	Botswana
Luke Mhaka	Zimbabwe
Fred Nyirenda	Malawi

Antoni du Toit	South Africa
Andrei Rozanov (RHC & host)	South Africa (RHC)
Cathy Clarke	South Africa
Bernard Waruru (RHC-EAH))	Kenya
Achraf Katar (RHC-NAH)	Tunisia
Sylvain Alongo (RHC-CAH)	Congo DR
Mary Steverink-Mosugu (proj. coord.)	Netherlands
Phanuel Ayuke (res. person)	Kenya
Samuel Mesele (res. person-online)	Nigeria
Adam Csorba (res. Person-ref sites)	Hungary
Jeroen Huising (res. person)	Nigeria

Programme:

Field campaign management -Day 1			
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
9:00 am	Registration: Lombardi building room 3001, Victoria str.		
9:30 – 9:50	Welcome and Introduction of country supervisors, RHC and facilitators	Dr. A. Rozanov	
9:50 – 10:15	Introduction of the project	Dr Mary Steverink-Mosugu	
10.15 – 10:35	General introduction of the field campaign, and implementation plan	Dr Jeroen Huising	
10:35 – 10:45	Purpose, objectives and expected results of the training programme	Dr Jeroen Huising	
10:45 – 11:15	COFFEE BREAK		
11:15 – 12:45	Protocol for the field survey	Dr Jeroen Huising	https://tinyurl.com/5n7u7yww https://vimeo.com/showcase/9366983 (Password: s4a): 1 - materials, 2 - sampling layout, 3 - using auger, 4 - using pipe, 5 - using spade, 6 - bagging & labelling, 7 - special situations, 8 - soil depth assessment, 9 - stoniness, 10 - drainage
12:45 – 1:45	LUNCH		

1:45 – 2:30	Protocol for field campaign management	Dr Jeroen Huising	
2:30 – 3:30	Barcodes generation	Dr Huising	https://tag.qed.ai
3:30 – 4:30	Field campaign management: planning and budgeting	Dr Jeroen Huising Dr Andrei Rozanov	
4:30 – 4:40	Feedbacks and Remarks	Dr Andrei Rozanov	

Day 2 Field survey: tools and techniques

Time	Activity	Person(S) In Charge	Remarks
9:00 – 10:00	SDMT: General introduction and registration of users	Mr Phaniel Ayuka	Video available on VIMEO (see link above)
10:00 – 11:00	SDMT – Sampling point validation	Dr Jeroen Huising & Phaniel Ayuka	
11:00 – 11:30	COFFEE BREAK		
11:30 – 1.00	SDMT – Surveyors application, Job assignment, and Quality control,	Jeroen Huising & Phaniel Ayuka	
1:00 – 1:45	LUNCH		
1:45 – 2:45	Introduction to the SOP and ODK forms	Dr Samuel Mesele	Online - demonstrating ODK forms
2:45 – 3.45	Hands-on experience with the use of the ODK forms - registration on ONA platform	Dr Jeroen Huising & Dr Sam Mesele	
3:45 – 4:30	Introduction to planning and budgeting for country field campaign	Dr Jeroen Huising	
4:30 – 4:45	Feedback and remarks	Dr Andrei Rozanov	

Day 3 Field survey of the reference sites

Time	Activity	Person(S) In Charge	Remarks
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9:00 – 9:30	Introduction of the reference sites	Dr Adam Csorba	
9:40 – 10:40	Protocols and tools	Dr Ádám Csorba	
10:40 – 11:00	COFFEE BREAK		
11:00 – 1:00	Site selection, planning and organization	Dr Adam Csorba	
1:00 – 1:45	LUNCH		
1:45 – 3:30	Field campaign planning and budgeting (hands on)	Jeroen Huising	Group exercise; Example for South Africa worked out in plenary
3:30 – 4:00	Discussing implementation plan – SAH (prioritization) – contract negotiation; planning and preparation EAH, NAH and CAH	Jeroen Huising	
4:00 – 4:15	Feedbacks, Closing Remarks	Dr Andrei Rozano	

Day 4 FIELD VISIT			
Time	Activity	Person(S) In Charge	Remarks
8:00 – 10:00	Travel to the Field Experimental Site	Dr. Cathy Clarke	
10:00 – 12:00	Demonstration of the SOP for the field survey	Dr Jeroen Huising	
12:00 – 1:00	LUNCH		
1:00 – 3:00	Demonstration of field survey protocols for the reference site	Dr Ádám Csorba	
3:00 – 3:05	Closing remarks	Dr Andrei Rozanov	
3:05 – 5:00	Return trip	Dr. Cathy Clarke	

Purpose and objective of the training workshop

This was the fourth workshop in line dealing with training for the field campaign. That is, training on the protocols and tools to be used for the field survey itself and the instructions and use of tools for the management of the field campaign. Other than the case for West Africa the country supervisors from all countries from the southern Africa region were invited. Moreover, the regional hub coordinators for the East Africa, North Africa and Central Africa hub were invited for this workshop such that they could acquaint themselves with the protocols and tools for the field campaign as well and such that they could start with preparations for the field campaign in their own regions.

The protocol and SOP for the field survey have been adjusted since the workshop in Burkina Faso and we were still seeking feedback from the workshop to whether the protocols are readily understood and whether the protocol are applicable to the conditions and situation in the southern Africa region. Likewise, regarding the instructions for field campaign management, we want to know whether these are actionable (applicable to the south African context).

Furthermore, the workshop aims at getting a clear idea on how the campaign can be organised in the various countries (modus operandi) and to get a clear idea of the budget requirements and whether the available budget would meet the budget requirements for the field campaign.

Another objective of the workshop is for people to physically meet and get to know one and each other to promote the good collaboration between members of the project. That is for the country supervisors meeting each other and interacting with their regional hub coordinator as well as with the overall coordinators of the field campaign, and the regional hub coordinators interacting between themselves and with the central coordinating office. From this perspective it was a pity that Samuel Mesele was not able to obtain his visa for South Africa. Luckily, we were able to arrange for Phanuel Ayuke to stand in as a resource person for the SDMT and we arranged for Samuel Mesele to present online.

We thank Stellenbosch University for hosting this event and especially Andrei Rozanov, Jacomi van der Merwe and Cathy Clarke for making all the arrangements and being such good hosts. It was thoroughly enjoyed by all participants

Outcome and conclusions:

1. All participants received the updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0) and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 2.0). For the Portuguese speaking countries the English version will not work for the field surveyors and a Portuguese version will be required. We have been discussing how this could best be done and our communication officer, Abraham Abhishek has put this already in motion. It is good to have the booklets for reference. A5 is a handy format, and we cannot rely on people to access the information online only.
2. The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that we presented. That is, the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that seems to be well designed and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable. As in the earlier workshops some people had some difficulty picking it up; the younger people in general seemed to have less problems. It will require a lot of exercise before the tools can be used effectively and it require the CS to arrange

for technical support in using these tools locally or to be provided by the regional hub coordinator.

3. The same applies to the template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign. The template provides a good insight in the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters is the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day). The template provides a way of calculating the sampling efficiency, but it is only by experience in the field that a correct estimated can be made. We elaborated the budget for the field campaign in South Africa in plenary, to illustrate how the template works, while the country supervisors worked on their own budget. The budget for RSA is seems to be a quite realistic one (confirmed as such by the participants from RSA), whereas the results for the other countries at the end of the exercise was out of bounce (far beyond the available funds). Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets to be discussed in two weeks after closing of the workshop. The budget for South Africa is presented in Appendix 1.
4. There was quite some confusion about the actual number of sampling points (the number of PSUs) for the region and therefore for the individual countries as well. This is because there are different version of the sampling design and there is confusion about the 'safe' (safe 1) and 'unsafe' (safe 2) sampling points and between the 'planned' and 'backup' points. This resulted in a lot of discussion and people insisting that the number of points should be reduced to get to the 20,000 points being mentioned in the grant agreement. The correct number of points and the correct location is indicated by the SDMT and this will serve as the ultimate source of correct data. The SDMT has a download function for if you want to work with the data offline. However, the SDMT is still in testing phase and not all have access to the data. We have provided all country supervisors with the sampling point data for their specific countries. It concerns the 'planned' and 'backup' PSU location in separate files and 'planned' and 'backup' SSU data in one single file. The SSU data still contains four 'backup' points per PSU whereas in the SDMT This has been reduced to seven. So, it still may give some confusion. The RHC has been provided the data for the whole region.
5. Notes with respect to the survey protocol, instruction videos, SOP and ODK form:
 - a. The videos still mention the 2.5m distance from the central point from the plot. This should be changed to 2m according to the revised protocol.
 - b. Instruct to take 1 kg of soil per samples to be taken from the field, if the required amount for the soil analysis is 500g and if the idea is to temporarily store 500g locally as backup for in case anything goes wrong with the analysis. This is going to amount to a large volume of soil to be shipped internally within the country, possibly within the region and to South Africa, and will have financial implications. The 500g needed for wet chem analysis is based on what is customary and not on the amounts of soil required sec for the analysis according to the protocols. Has high priority to be sorted out finally.
 - c. In the relevant video mention and explain the various causes of soil depth restrictions, rather than just say 'indicate cause of restriction'

- d. For the observation of surface stoniness, the protocol says observe a circular area with radius of 10m or more and the SOP says observe an area within a 16m radius. Should be consistently put a 10m radius (and leave out the “or more”)
 - e. The SDMT needs to be available on a secured platform (website), otherwise you might have difficulty accessing the URL. Like in South Africa I was blocked using the site by ‘flex.vodacom’ and I could not find a ‘way around’. Just a reminder that this needs to be thoroughly checked in every country once we have SDMT on the production platform (and make sure the site is secured).
 - f. There was a lot of resistance against filling in data on texture and stoniness and other, that is not really needed because it is determined anyhow in the lab analysis or that can be determined otherwise. Same was felt on the recording of data on land cover and land use, of which people did not see the relevance. In general, the ODK form was considered to elaborate, and fear was that it would take too much time in the field.
 - g. ‘Vines’ to be included in the options for Lifeform in the ODK form.
 - h. Suggestion was made to put/include instructions in the ODK form (review and see where this would make sense)
6. Using the ‘consent form’ for getting consent from farmers or farm managers in the field is not going to work in case of South Africa. There are many large farms in South Africa for which you would need prior consent to enter the farm. Just showing up at the gate will generally not work and you might not find any person to sign the ‘consent form’. So as not to lose too much time you need to call them in advance and to arrange the visit. This means that consent is given on the phone and often there may not be an opportunity to get the consent form signed. That implies an alternative need to be found for getting the consent (for taking samples and making the data public), and this might be through recording the conversation on phone or getting written confirmation through Whatsapp, email or other. Getting the contacts Finding and calling these farm managers takes a lot of effort and that needs to be considered in preparation for the field survey. The RHC is requested to find a workable solution. It would also imply that surveyors can move straight to the back-up SSU locations when in the field without having to reject the points not provided access to in the ODK form.
7. Notes with respect to the contract with the CS regarding the outsourcing procedure and conflict of interest: It is suggested to include in the contract with the CS a statement that the CS will follow the procedures as stated in the instructions for field campaign management for selecting the surveyor and that the CS will follow an open and fair process and will avoid any conflict of interest. There should also be a statement in general that the CS has read and understood the protocols and that he/she has familiarized him/herself with the tools and agrees to follow procedures. The same should apply to the surveyor’s contract (letter of agreement).
8. Questions were raised about the CS also having a role as field surveyor. It is relevant especially for the countries with a small number of sampling points to improve efficiency and reduce cost. The question is also how this can be formally arranged. The SDMT does not pose a problem as we have already configured it such that the same person can have different roles (in response to similar questions earlier). Point here is whether we would allow the RHC to act as CS for any

of the countries within his/her region, or whether a CS can be a supervisor for more than one country. In this case the Southern Africa Hub coordinator/CS for South Africa could be the CS for Namibia and Botswana. This might also be a solution for Lesotho and Eswatini. It might possibly also save some cost in view of the OH charges that we then do not have to pay.

9. The tentative budget has been done for all the countries of the southern Africa region. All of them showed budget that exceed the available funds, to varying degrees, however. All countries would review their budgets and report back and we planned an online meeting within two weeks' time to discuss and see whether we can finalize. It should be noted that the time for the validation of the PSUs is not included explicitly in budget calculations. Validation and preparation for the field work will require a lot of work especially in South Africa. There are doubts the assumed/proposed efficiency of being able to do 3 PSU's in two days on average can be realized. It would suggest that CS should plan for a testing period, based on which then the final budget can be made. At least CS should study the distances between the PSU and get a better idea of the travel time required to visit the sampling sites. In general, there is a feeling that the survey and ODK form are too elaborate and there was a push towards simplifying the form. Again, practice will show what is possible. We will adjust the budget still with respect to the cost of shipping the samples to the ARC, Pretoria, which will be much less than for the other regions in Africa.
10. The first site of the field was at a vineyard, and it illustrated the point that getting access to this kind of sites is not easy (though people are generally not unwilling). The point also illustrated how complex the soil can be. The soils on these farms are generally worked to one meter depth, lime applied, etc. to make them suitable for viticulture. It results in a lot of short-distance variation and make profile description quite complicated. It also implies that the interpretation of the soil data will be quite difficult without the contextual information. Digging the minipits and getting the BD samples done took far too much time such that it was suggested to have only one minipit, but that samples are going to be taken from the three sites. Also, it was suggested to do a profile description of the minipit, because that gives already so much information on the type of soil that is found.

Appendix 1. Tentative budget for the field campaign in South Africa

	Country/region	South Africa
	Country supervisor	
	Number PSU (original design)	339
A	Number of PSU (after validation)	339
B	Number of TSU (sampling locations)	1356
C	Number of samples to be taken	2712
D	Number of samples for shipment (internally)	2712
E	Nr kg to be shipped	1356
F	Total number of days field survey	245

Number of teams conducting field survey	22
Number of days in the field per team	12
Number of teams in the field per month	2.2

Key figures and reference data

Number of TSU per PSU	4
Number of samples per location	2
Weight sample from the field	500
Cost shipment per kg internally (\$)	\$1
Cost sample preparation (\$)	\$0.5
Cost equipment for a team	\$400
Cost materials/supplies per SP	\$1.67
Cost travel (car) per km (incl. fuel, driver, car hire)	\$1.00
Average time for survey PSU (days) *	0.72
Percentage time allocation CS of time for field survey (days)	20%
Daily fee country supervisor (\$)	\$150
Window of operation (months)	10

* The average time to survey one PSU depends on distance (km) to travel per day (viz., 70km) and time needed to travel that distance (viz., 2 hours), plus the time needed for conducting the survey of one PSU (viz., 3 hrs) and considering the time required to travel to and fro to the region (hrs) divided over the number of days spent in the field for that trip (in this case 1.5 hrs/day), divided by a 9 hrs workday

Budget available per sampling point (\$)	\$65.33
Overall budget avail. for campaign for the country	\$88,587
Overhead cahrges exec. agency (5)	10%
Net budget available for campaign	\$79,729

Total budget avail survey/campaign	\$79,729
Cost sample preparation	\$1,356
Cost shipment samples	\$1,356
Training/instruction survey teams	\$11,000
Equipment for field teams	\$1,200
Materials supplies field survey	\$2,266
Cost fee country supervisor	\$7,350
Available budget field survey	\$55,201
Avr bgt available per team	\$2,509
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$162.84

Available budget field survey per day	\$225.46
Daily allowance team leader	\$60

Daily allowance team members	\$75
Transport	
Transport by car	\$113
Motorcycle (field navigating)	\$20
Security / local guide	\$10
Estimated cost one day fieldwork	\$278
Difference avail. bgt and estimated cost field day	-\$52
Balance field campaign (total avail - projected cost, US\$)	-\$12,836

ANNEX G: Report Training workshop in Tunisia, NAH

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budgeting for Northern Africa Region

Date: 4 - 8 September 2022 at Institut des Régions Arides (IRA), Tunisia

Attendance:

Last name	First Name	Organization	Country
Boumaraf	Belgacem	Uni. Biskra	Algeria
Kotb	Mostafa	Uni. B. Suef	Egypt
Csorba	Adam	Szent István Univ.	Hungary
Ben Gamaa	Abdurahman	LCRSSS	Libya
Vall	Mohamed	Univ. Nouakchott	Mauritania
Ben Zhir	Khalid	INRA	Morocco
Huising	Jeroen	IITA	Nigeria
Mesele	Samuel	IITA	Nigeria
Attia	Rafla	DGACTA	Tunisia
Guimeur	Kamel	Uni. Biskra	Algeria
El Hamdi	Abdulraof	LCRSSS	Libya
Madi	Ali	NCAR	Libya
Ouessar	Mohamed	IRA	Tunisia
Dridi	Sana	DGACTA	Tunisia
Taboubi	Saber	CRDA Béja	Tunisia
Ijmali	Rouhia	CRDA Sidi Bouzid	Tunisia
Bouabid	Nabil	CRDA Medenine	Tunisia
Rtimi	Monem	CRDA Gabes	Tunisia
Katar	Achraf	IRA	Tunisia
Moussa	Mohamed	IRA	Tunisia
Chibani	Roukaya	IRA	Tunisia

Programme

Monday 05 September 2022: Field campaign management		
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE
9:00 am	Registration: IRA, ROUTE DE JORF KM 22, MEDENINE 4119, Tunisia	
9:30 – 9:50 am	Welcome and Introduction of country supervisors, RHC and facilitators	Mr. Gouider Atallah, DG IRA Prof Mohamed Moussa, Head LELCD Dr Rafla Attia, Dir. Soils, Tunisia Prof Mohamed Ouessar, NAH Coordinator
9:50 – 10:15 am	General introduction of the field campaign, and implementation plan	Dr Jeroen Huising
10.15 – 10:30 am	Purpose, objectives and expected results of the training programme	Dr Jeroen Huising
10:30 – 10:45 am	Introduction to the Protocol for the field survey -requirements and navigation	Dr Samuel Mesele
10:45 – 11:15 am	COFFEE BREAK	
11:15 – 12:45	Protocol for the field survey -keynotes and technicalities	Dr Samuel Mesele
12:45 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH	
1:45 – 2:30 pm	Protocol for field campaign management	Dr Jeroen Huising
2:30 – 3:30	Barcodes generation	Dr Samuel Mesele
3:30 – 4:30 pm	Field campaign management: planning and budgeting	Dr Jeroen Huising Prof Mohamed Ouessar
4:30 – 4:45 pm	Feedbacks and Remarks	Prof Mohamed Ouessar

Tuesday 06 September 2022: Field survey: tools and techniques		
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE
9:00 – 10:00am	SDMT: General introduction and registration of users	Dr Samuel Mesele
10:00 – 11:00 am	SDMT – Sampling point validation	Dr Jeroen Huising & Dr Samuel Mesele
11:00 – 11:30 am	COFFEE BREAK	
11:30 – 1.00 pm	SDMT – Surveyors application, Job assignment, and Quality control,	Group work
1:00 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH	
1:45 – 2:45 pm	Introduction to the SOP and ODK forms	Dr Samuel Mesele
2:45 – 3.45 pm	Hands-on experience with the use of the ODK forms -registration on Ona platform	Dr Jeroen Huising & Dr Sam Mesele
3:45 – 4:30 pm	Introduction to planning and budgeting for country field campaign	Dr Jeroen Huising
4:30 – 4:45 pm	Feedback and remarks	Prof Mohamed Ouessar

Wednesday 07 September 2022: Field survey of the reference sites		
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE
9:00 – 9:30 am	Introduction of the reference sites	Dr Adam Csorba
9:40 – 10:40 am	Protocols and tools	Dr Ádám Csorba
10:40 – 11:00 am	COFFEE BREAK	
11:00 – 1:00 pm	Site selection, planning and organization	Dr Adam Csorba
1:00 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH	
1:45 – 3:30 pm	Field campaign planning and budgeting (hands on)	Group
3:30 – 4:15 pm	Unfinished business, Feedbacks, Closing Remarks	Pr Mohamed Ouessar

Thursday 08 September 2022: FIELD VISIT		
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE
8:00 – 10:00 am	Travel to the Field Experimental Site	Prof Mohamed Ouessar & Eng. Achraf Katar
10:00 – 12:00	Demonstration of the SOP for the field survey	Dr. Jeroen Huising & Dr. Samuel Mesele
12:00 – 1:00 pm	LUNCH	
1:00 – 3:00 pm	Demonstration of field survey protocols for the reference site	Dr Ádám Csorba
3:00 – 3:05 pm	Closing remarks	Prof Mohamed Ouessar
3:05 – 5:00 pm	Return trip	Prof Mohamed Ouessar & Eng. Achraf Katar

Above is the original training programme. As the technical sessions took much longer than anticipated we had to reschedule. In the end, the Monday was spent mainly on the protocol for the field survey, the Tuesday on the SDMT, and the Wednesday afternoon was taken by the planning and budgeting exercise, with the Wednesday morning dedicated to the reference sites. On Thursday we went to the field for demonstration of how the survey of a standard sampling site and reference site is done, for which an actual sampling point location was selected and for which actual data was collected. After the field visit, we had a plenary session to explain and demonstrate the quality control procedures as it is implemented in the SDMT, based on the data that was collected in the field.

The closing event of the training workshop was the award ceremony in which the certificates of attendance were issued to all participants, organisers, and facilitators.

Friday 09 September 2022: Field Trip

A post-training field trip/ Free day will be organized. It will include:

- Visit tour by crossing the main natural and agro-ecological zones of the region: plain of Jeffara

(olive tree plantations, irrigated fields, etc.) and the mountains of Beni Khedache and Tataouine (picturesque views, traditional water harvesting, troglodytes, loess accumulations, etc.).

More details will be provided in the Field Tour Guide.

Purpose and objective of the training workshop

This was the fifth (5) workshop for capacity building and training for the field campaign. The training workshop included training on the protocols and tools to be used for the field survey for both standard sampling sites and reference sites and the instructions for, and use of tools for the management of the field campaign, including for planning and budgeting for the field campaign within the country. The country supervisors from all countries from the North Africa region were invited including their assistants.

The protocol and SOP for the field survey have been adjusted since the previous workshops in Burkina Faso and South Africa. They are now considered finalized in as far as the content (specifications) are concerned. We are still seeking feedback from the workshop participants on the whether the explanation is crisp and clear (and text and wording, especially for the Arabic translation in this case, and whether the protocols are applicable to the conditions and situation in the North Africa region. Likewise, regarding the instructions for field campaign management, we want to know whether these are actionable and applicable to the north African context.

Furthermore, the workshop aims at getting a clear idea of how the campaign can be organized in the various countries (*modus operandi*) and to get a clear idea of the budget requirements and to what extent the available budget would suffice.

Another objective of the workshop is for people to physically meet and get to know one another, so as to promote good collaboration between members of the project. That is for the country supervisors to meet each other and interact with their regional hub coordinator as well as with the overall coordinators of the field campaign.

We thank *Institut des Régions Arides* (IRA) for hosting this event and especially Prof Mohamed Ouessar and Katar Achraf for making all the arrangements and being such good hosts. It was unarguably enjoyed by all participants.

Outcome and conclusions:

1. All participants received the updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0), and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 3.0). The documents were made available in French, English, and Arabic and each participant was able to choose their preferred language.
2. The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that we presented. That is the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that seems to be well designed, and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable.

3. As in the earlier workshops, quite some people had difficulty picking up how the tools work and in using them. The younger people in general seemed to have fewer problems. This is related to everything being formalized and standardized (protocols and procedures) and everything being done digitally. Some were hampered by their rather old computers and phones that do not meet the specifications, not being able to download the apps for example, with the result that they were not able to follow instructions and do the exercises. It will require a lot of exercise before the tools can be used effectively and some have already claimed new computers and phones. It requires the CS to arrange for technical support in using these tools, to be provided locally or by the regional hub coordinator.
4. The same applies to the template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign. The template provides a good insight into the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters is the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day). The template provides a way of calculating the sampling efficiency, but it is only by experience in the field that a correct estimate can be made. Like what was done in South Africa, we elaborated the budget for the field campaign in Tunisia in plenary, to illustrate how the template works, while the country supervisors worked on their own budget. The budget estimates for Tunisia IRA and the other countries at the end of the exercise were far beyond the available funds. Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets to be discussed two weeks after the closing of the workshop. The budget for Tunisia is presented in Appendix 1.
5. Notes with respect to the survey protocol, instruction videos, SOP and ODK form:
 - a. Instruct to take 1 kg of soil per samples to be taken from the field, if the required amount for the soil analysis is 500g and if the idea is to temporarily store 500g locally as backup for in case anything goes wrong with the analysis. The budget implication is yet to be completely sorted out
 - b. Check French translations for loamy and silty. Both are called Limoneux in French. Maybe add for the loamy class: comparable amounts of clay, silt and sand fraction (“quantité comparable de fractions d'argile, de limon et de sable), and for the silty texture class add ‘elevated silt content (“teneur élevée en limon”)
 - c. Put ‘Vines’ in the lifeform category rather than the land use category
6. Using the ‘consent form’ for getting consent from farmers or farm managers in the field is not going to work as it is seen for north Africa, in addition to previous similar experiences in West and South Africa. Farmers are generally afraid to sign such documents as they easily misinterpret such consent to be giving away the ownership of their farms. Consent could generally be given but not formal and in cases where consent is not given the surveyors should go for the alternative backup points.
7. The tentative budget has been done for all the countries of the northern Africa region. All of them showed budgets that exceed the available funds, generally by a factor two. All countries would review their budgets and report back and we planned an online meeting within two

weeks' time to discuss and see whether we can finalize. It should be noted that the time for the validation of the PSUs is not included explicitly in budget calculations but is taken to be an integral work of the country supervisor.

8. Field survey was conducted in one of the actual sampling points close to Médenine. The point illustrated how complex the soil can be. The data was recorded and uploaded to the SDMT where the quality control was later done. The quality control procedures were explained and demonstrated to all participants using the sampled point.
9. The weather condition is harsh and directly impacts on the amount of time people can spend on the field. This will impact on the number PSU that can be done in a day. In wintertime the conditions are more favourable. Generally, in summertime the fieldwork is possible between 6.00 to 10.00 only. We will see what can be done during wintertime, but it may not be possible to achieve the same efficiencies as we are getting in other parts of Africa.
10. Organising the field campaign making use of independent surveyors is considered difficult in Tunisia and other countries in the North Africa region (they might not even be allowed to contract people from outside the organisation). Rather use is made of skilled people from their own or partner organisations. In that case the official per diem rates need to be paid, which is like to make the exercise rather expensive. The possible implications need to be understood and the solutions need to be found for each country individually and need to be reflected in the implementation plan and budget for the field campaign before the contracts can be signed. That also applies to the institutional cost and possible charges by government that may severe inflate the cost of the field campaign (e.g., in Egypt where the government will take 20% of each international contract).
11. The land and soil conditions, especially of the dryland areas, will have impact on the execution and implementation of the protocols and herewith also on the data that is to be collected. The petrocalcic horizons, which are ubiquitous in this region will not allow for a soil profile description. Even for the minipits, it will be difficult to dig these up to 50cm depth in many places and it will generally not be possible to take BD samples (which was the prime objective for the reference sites, until recently). For the surface ring samples soils you will need to bring water to wet the soil before you can take the samples. Soil depth will be termed very shallow because it is often not possible the auger beyond 10cm, whereas the effective soil depth is deeper, and roots will also be able to penetrate to deeper layers. In summary, these kinds of conditions add to the complexity, both to the data collection as well as the interpretation of the data.
12. The sampling design might not be most adequate for the type of landscape we have seen during the excursion. Agricultural fields are found in small spots, generally within the small dryland valleys. They fields are very small in size and likely to be missed by the sampling design. The PSUs, if they can be found at all in these landscapes will likely be rejected in the validation process. The validation procedure is likely also to take extra time because it will require to look and the TSU whether they fall upon these small within agricultural fields. Even the 1-ha SSU will be too large.

Appendix 1. Tentative budget for the field campaign in Tunisia

This is the budget estimate for the field campaign in Tunisia, whereby the Tunisian team is asked to indicate the cost for the various cost items (like the cost for transport per km, cost for preparation of one sample, daily fee for country supervisor), to indicate the time needed for coordination and supervision and others. The aim is not to come to a realistic budget at once, but to make them aware of the risk of overbudgeting; to make them cost sensitive and to impart on them the need for cost reduction.

For Tunisia the estimate cost is double of the funds that are available and the same resulted for the other countries as well. It is made clear that this will not be accepted by the project.

Country/region	Tunisia
Country supervisor	Attia Rafla Ms
Number PSU (original design)	45
A Number of PSU (after validation)	45
B Number of TSU (sampling locations)	180
C Number of samples to be taken	360
D Number of samples for shipment (internally)	360
E Nr kg to be shipped	360
F Total number of days field survey	34
Number of teams conducting field survey	3
Number of days in the field per team	12
Number of teams in the field per month	0.6
Key figures and reference data	
Number of TSU per PSU	4
Number of samples per location	2
Weight sample from the field	1000
Cost shipment per kg internally (\$)	\$1
Cost sample preparation (\$)	\$4.0
Cost equipment for a team ¹	\$460
Cost materials/supplies per SP	\$1.67
Cost travel (car) per km (incl. fuel, driver, car hire) ²	\$1.50
Average time for survey PSU (days) ³	0.75

¹ This includes US\$260 for a smartphone, US\$120 for a GPS device, \$20 for a powerbank and US\$50 in total for tools like a spade, bucket, knife etc. There are options to reduce, especially do away with the GPS if MAPS.ME can be used

² Seems on the high side and needs to be reassessed based on calculations for fuel consumption, depreciation and maintenance cost or indeed actual cost for car hire.

³ Is based on assumptions we have used for other countries as well, but should be based on the actual planning of field trips within the different regions of the country.

Percentage time allocation CS of time for field survey (days)	50%
Daily fee country supervisor (\$)	\$150
Window of operation (months)	5
Budget available per sampling point (\$)	\$65.33
Overall budget avail. For campaign for the country	\$11,759
Overhead charges exec. Agency (5)	20%
Net budget available for campaign	\$9,408
Total budget avail survey/campaign	\$9,408
Cost sample preparation	\$1,440
Cost shipment samples	\$360
Training/instruction survey teams	\$1,500
Equipment for field teams	\$460
Materials supplies field survey	\$301
Cost fee country supervisor	\$2,550
Available budget field survey	\$2,797
Avr bgt available per team	\$932
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$62.15
Available budget field survey per day	\$82.87
Daily allowance team leader	\$100
Daily allowance team members	\$60
Total field staff	
Transport by car ⁴	\$225
Motorcycle (field navigating)	\$0
Total transport	
Security / local guide	\$10
Estimated cost one day fieldwork	\$395
Total budget available for field survey	\$2,817
Total estimated cost field survey	\$13,430
Balance field campaign (total avail – projected cost, US\$)	-\$10,613
Total cost field campaign (incl. OH)	\$22,372
Estimated cost per sampling point	\$124.29

⁴ The cost is determined by the actual km that a team need to travel in the field. For this exercise estimated at 150km on average per day. Needs to be assessed base on the actual planning of the field trip and might be less or more depending on the configuration of the PSUs in the various regions

ANNEX H: Report Training workshop in Kenya (EAH)

Soils4Africa Field Campaign – protocols and tools, planning and budgeting for East Africa Region

Date: 8 - 11 November 2022

Venue: Fish Eagle Inn, Naivasha, Kenya Authors: Jeroen Huising and Samuel Mesele

Attendance:

S/N	FIRST NAMES	LAST NAME	INSTITUTE	COUNTRY	CAPACITY
1	Tolera Abera	Goshu	EIAR, Ambo Agric Research Centre	Ethiopia	CS
2	Sibaway B	Mwango	TARI-Mlingano	Tanzania, Tanga	CS
3	Moses	Isabirye	Busitema University	Uganda	CS
4	Marie-Chantal	Niyuhire	ISABU	Burundi, Bujumbura	CS
5	Vicky	Ruganzu	Rwanda Agricultural Board	Rwanda, Kigali	CS
6	Isaac	Bazugba	Ministry of Agric/ Nile Agrotech	South Sudan	CS
7	Abdelmagid Ali	Elmobarak	ARC, Land & Water research centre	Sudan	CS
8	Mustafe	Jirde	Gollis University, Centre land and water	Somalia	CS
9	Dermes	Sultan	Ministry of Agric	Eritrea	CS (ABSENT)
10	Mohamed	Egueh	Monistry of Agric	Djibouti	CS
15	Michael	Okoti	KALRO	Kenya	RHC
16	Benard	Waruru	KALRO	Kenya	CS
17	Fredrick	Wandera	KALRO	Kenya	CS Ass.
18	David	Kamau	KALRO	Kenya	Head Department
19	Lucas	Tanui	KALRO	Kenya	Member team Kenya
20	Kennedy	Muchukuri	KALRO	Kenya	Member team Kenya
21	Angela	Maina	KALRO	Kenya	Member team Kenya
22	Cynthia	Achieng	KALRO	Kenya	Member team Kenya
23	Eliud	Keriger	KALRO	Kenya	DG KALRO
24	Carolyne	Minayo	KALRO	Kenya	PA to DG
25	Brian	Rotich	Chuka University	Kenya	TF reference sites
26	Justine	Phenson	Chuka University	Tanzania	TF reference sites
27	Evans	Mutuma	Chuka University	Kenya	TF reference sites
28	Adam	Csorba	Uni MATE	Hungary	Resource person
29	Erika	Micheli	University MATE	Hungary	Resource person
30	Samuel	Mesele	IITA	Nigeria	Resource person
31	Jeroen	Huising	IITA	Nigeria	Resource person
32	Caroline	Owuor	IITA	Kenya	
33	Phanuel	Ayuke	IITA	Kenya	Resource person

Programme:

Tuesday 08 November 2022: Welcome, Introduction, protocols and tools			
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
8.15 – 8.50 am	Registration	M/s Annah Sang	
8.50 – 9.20 am	Welcome and Introduction of country supervisors, RHC and facilitators	Dr David Kamau	
9:20 – 9:50 am	Welcome address and official opening of the workshop	Dr. Eliud Kireger – Director General KALRO	
9:50 – 10:30 am	General introduction of the field campaign, and implementation plan -purpose, objectives and expected outcome of the training workshop	Dr Jeroen Huising	
10:30 – 11:00 am	COFFEE BREAK		
11:00 – 12:45	Protocol for the field survey requirements and navigation keynotes and technicalities	Dr Samuel Mesele	
12:45 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH		
1:45 – 2:30 pm	Protocol for field campaign management Barcode generation	Dr Samuel Mesele Dr Jeroen Huising	
2:30 – 4.30	Electronic data collection using ODK and the SOP - Installing ODK-Collect and selecting the forms, making the forms available to surveyors - Demonstration use of forms in ODK collect - Explaining SOP going through the forms	Dr Samuel Mesele Dr Jeroen Huising	
4:30 – 4:45 pm	Feedbacks and Remarks	Dr Michael Okoti	

Wednesday 09 November 2022: Survey data management tool (SDMT)			
TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
9:00 am	Registration :	KALRO	
9:30 – 9:50 am	Overview of the SDMT and its functionalities -and the surveyor's application webpage	Ms Caroline Owuor	

9:50 – 10:30am	SDMT Presentation and demonstration - Sampling point validation - Surveyors application and onboarding of surveyors	Mr Phaniel Ayuka Dr Jeroen Huising	
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break		

11:30 – 12:45 am	SDMT Presentation and demonstration - Job assignment - Quality control - Onboarding of country supervisors	Mr Phaniel Ayuka Ms Caroline Ayuka	
12:45 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH		
1:45 – 3:30 pm	- Hands-on SDMT - Sampling point validation	Mr Phaniel Ayuka Ms Caroline Ayuka Dr Jeroen Huising	
3:30 – 4:00 pm	Feedbacks and Remarks	KALRO	

Thursday 10 September 2022: Field survey of the references and field campaign management

TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
9:00 – 9:30 am	Introduction of the reference sites	Dr Adam Csorba	
9:40 – 10:40 am	Protocols and tools	Dr Ádám Csorba	
10:40 – 11:00 am	COFFEE BREAK		
11:00 – 1:00 pm	Site selection, planning and organization	Dr Adam Csorba	
1:00 – 1:45 pm	LUNCH		
1:45 – 3:30 pm	Field campaign planning and budgeting (hands-on)	Dr. Jeroen Huising	
3:30 – 4:15 pm	Unfinished business, Feedback, Closing Remarks	KALRO	

Friday 11 September 2022: FIELD VISIT

TIME	ACTIVITY	PERSON(S) IN CHARGE	REMARKS
8:00 – 10:00 am	Travel to the Field Experimental Site	KALRO	
10:00 – 12:00	Demonstration of the SOP for the field survey	Dr Jeroen Huising & Dr Samuel Mesele	
12:00 – 1:00 pm	LUNCH		
1:00 – 3:00 pm	Demonstration of field survey protocols for the reference site	Dr. Ádám Csorba	
3:00 – 3:05 pm	Closing remarks	KALRO	
3:05 – 5:00 pm	Return trip	KALRO	

Above is the original training programme. Due to flight cancellations and the associated difficulty in finding an alternate route and flight rescheduling, Jeroen and Sam and the participant from Burundi could not arrive before the start of the workshop. They are only able to arrive towards the close of work on the first day of the workshop. The training programme was therefore adjusted. Tuesday was for the opening ceremony, reference site activity, and introduction of the SDMT. On Wednesday the SDMT session continued for the first part of the morning session, the rest of the day was devoted to the protocol for the field survey and how to generate barcodes for sample labels. On Thursday, we focussed on standard operating procedures, the ODK forms, budgeting, and planning for the field campaign in each country. On Friday we went to the field for a demonstration of how the survey of a standard sampling site and reference site is done, for which an actual sampling point location was selected and for which actual data was collected. After the field visit, we had a plenary session to explain and demonstrate the quality control procedures as it is implemented in the SDMT, based on the data that was collected in the field.

Purpose and objective of the training workshop

This was the sixth (6) workshop for capacity building and training for the field campaign. The training workshop included training on the protocols and tools to be used for the field survey for both standard sampling sites and reference sites and the instructions for, and use of tools for the management of the field campaign, including for planning and budgeting for the field campaign within the country. The country supervisors from all countries from the East Africa region were invited and they were all present except for Eritrea (absent with notification).

The final version of the protocols and SOP for the field survey had been printed and presented to all the participants, including the instructions for managing the field campaign. We provided the Sudan representative with an Arabic version of the documents, and we had also a few French copies distributed for those that are more familiar in French.

The aim is to familiarize all participants with the various tools that are used for the field campaign, such that they will be able to use the tools independently and be able to instruct the surveyors in their own country as well. We had a large contingent of people from Kenya, the Regional Hub Coordinator, to be trained such that they would be able to provide support the countries within their region on technical matters when required.

The workshop further aims at getting a clear idea of how the campaign can be organized in the various countries (modus operandi) and to get a clear idea of the budget requirements and to what extent the available budget would suffice. With each of the CSs we had individual discussions on the conditions and situation in their country and what kind of arrangement they had in mind for organising the field campaign, and possible contractual arrangements were discussed. The budgeting exercise is aimed at making people aware of the budget constraint we are having, to temper their expectations and to still get their final commitment to do the field campaign being aware of these constraints (such that we have a basis for negotiation)

Another objective of the workshop is for people to physically meet and get to know one another, to promote good collaboration between members of the project. That is for the country supervisors to meet each other and interact with their regional hub coordinator as well as with the overall coordinators of the field campaign.

We thank Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) for hosting this event and especially Dr Michael Okoti and Dr Bernard Waruru for making all the arrangements and being such good hosts. It was immensely enjoyed by all participants.

Outcome and conclusions:

1. All participants received the updated booklets (A5 format) of the Protocol for Field Survey (version 3.0), Protocol for Field Survey Management (version 2.0), and the Standard Operating Procedure for the field survey (version 3.0). The documents were made available in French, English, and Arabic and each participant was able to choose their preferred language.
2. The participants were impressed with the tools and the apps that we presented. That is the app for generating QR codes, the ODK form that was well designed, and especially the SDMT tool that facilitates many of the tasks of the country supervisor (and regional hub coordinator) and makes them quite doable. Appendix 1 shows the screenshot of some of the appreciation messages from the participants.
3. As in the earlier workshops, quite some people had difficulty picking up how the tools work and in using them. The younger people in general seemed to have fewer problems. This is related to everything being formalized and standardized (protocols and procedures) and everything is done digitally. It will require a lot of exercises before the tools can be used effectively. It requires the CS to arrange for technical support in using these tools, to be provided locally or by the regional hub coordinator.
4. Some had difficulty, while filling the form for the field survey, to download or get the coordinates because of their rather old phones that did not meet the specifications. It illustrates the importance that surveyors need to have the proper equipment, but also that these are tested well before going to the field. Some have already claimed new computers and phones. There is budget for phones and other needed equipment and that should be used.
5. The template for the planning and budgeting of the field campaign is also considered complicated but provides a good insight into the different cost items for the field campaign and makes it possible to draw up a good budget. One of the most critical parameters is the time required on average to do one PSU (or how many sampling points one survey team can do in a day). The template provides a way of calculating the sampling efficiency, but it is only by experience in the field that a correct estimate can be made. Like what was done in previous workshops, we elaborated the budget for the field campaign in Kenya in plenary, to illustrate how the template works, while the country supervisors worked on their own budget. The budget estimates for KALRO Kenya and the other countries at the end of the exercise were far beyond the available funds (twice the available budget). And that was also the case for the draft budgets for the other countries. One of the issues in Kenya budget was that they want to use their own staff for the field survey and want to apply the official per diem rates (for staff of the rank of Bernard Waruru who is a senior officer) which would make the cost for the operation of the field teams per day too high, with even not having made any provision for covering for salary cost. It shows how complicated this issue is and that the CS needs to look for alternative ways to reduce costs (e.g., by making use of local extension agents). Country supervisors were given the assignment to work on their country budgets to be discussed two weeks after the closing of the workshop. The discrepancy between the projected budget and the available funds is very large and it will not be possible to reconcile it apart from maybe in special cases (smaller countries). The budget for Kenya is presented in Appendix 2.

6. No further changes are recommended with respect to the survey protocols, instruction manual for country supervisors, instruction videos, SOP and ODK form.
7. Using the 'consent form' for getting consent from farmers or farm managers in the field is not going to work for Kenya, like the for other countries as we experienced in West, South, and North Africa. In this case it took us over an hour to get consent from the farmer because the farmer himself was not present on the farm and because there had been issues over land recently people are very suspicious the sign anything (even our presence in the area created suspicion). One farmer got very angry at his wife for allowing us even on the farm. (Farmers are generally afraid to sign such documents as they easily misinterpret such consent to be giving away the ownership of their farms.) So, the advice is that consent should generally be given but not formally. In cases where it takes a considerable amount of time to get consent, the surveyors should go for the alternative backup point.
8. The tentative budget has been done for all the countries of the east Africa region. All of them showed budgets that exceed the available funds, generally by a factor of two. All countries would review their budgets and report back. It should be noted that the time for the validation of the PSUs is not included explicitly in budget calculations but is taken to be an integral work of the country supervisor.
9. Field survey was conducted in one of the actual sampling points close to Naivasha. The point illustrated how dry and compact the soil can be with extreme difficulty in augering. The data was recorded and uploaded to the SDMT where quality control was later done. The quality control procedures were explained and demonstrated to all participants using the sampled point.
10. We conducted a navigation exercise but at the place where the workshop was being held and, in the field, navigating to the points to be sampled. In both cases people were not able to converge to the same point within 20m accuracy. As a consequence we are going to accept points sampled in the field if they are within 20m of the planned sampling point location

Appendix 1. Some testimonials of the workshop participants

Appendix 2. Tentative budget for the field campaign in Kenya

Country/region	Kenya
Country supervisor	Bernard Waruru
Number PSU (original design)	103
Number of PSU (after validation)	103
Number of TSU (sampling locations)	412
Number of samples to be taken	824
Number of samples for shipment (internally)	824
Nr kg to be shipped	824
Total number of days field survey	83
Number of teams conducting field survey	6
Number of days in the field per team	14
Number of teams in the field per month	1
Total budget avail survey	\$22,879
Cost sample preparation	\$1,648
Cost shipment samples	\$824
Training/instruction survey teams	\$3,000
Equipment for field teams	\$800
Materials supplies field survey	\$688
Cost fee country supervisor	\$3,735
Available budget field survey	\$12,183
Avr bgt available per team	\$2,031
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$118.28

Key figures and reference data

Number of TSU per PSU	4
Number of samples per location	2
Weight sample from the field (g)	1000
Cost shipment per kg internally (\$)	\$1
Cost sample preparation (\$)	\$2.0
Cost equipment for a team	\$400
Cost materials/supplies per SP	\$1.67
Cost travel (car) per km (incl. fuel, driver, car hire)	\$1.00
Average time for survey PSU (days)	0.80
Percentage time allocation CS of time for field survey (days)	30%
Daily fee country supervisor (\$)	\$150

Window of operation (months) 6

Budget available per sampling point (\$)	\$65.33
Overall budget avail. for campaign for the country	\$26,916
Overhead cahrges exec. agency (5)	15%
Net budget available for campaign	\$22,879
OH charges (10%) on total direct costs	\$6,633
Total budget avail survey	\$22,879
Cost sample preparation	\$1,648
Cost shipment samples	\$824
Training/instruction survey teams	\$3,000
Equipment for field teams	\$800
Materials supplies field survey	\$688
Cost fee country supervisor	\$3,735
Available budget field survey	\$12,183
Avr bgt available per team	\$2,031
Avr bgt available per primary sampling unit	\$118.28
Available budget field survey per day	\$147.85
Daily allowance team leader	\$85
Daily allowance team members	\$100
Total field staff	
Transport by car	\$200
Motorcycle (field navigating)	\$10
Total transport	
Security / local guide	\$10
Estimated cost one day fieldwork / total FC	\$405
Difference avail. bgt and estimated cost field day	-\$257
Balance field campaign (total avail - projected cost, US\$)	-\$21,343

Pictures of participants and resource persons taken during the fieldwork in Naivasha